

**COMPARATIVE GENOME AND PROTEOME
ANALYSIS of *Labeo rohita* from HALDA RIVER**

MS. THESIS

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Dedicated To
My Family Members,
Our Beloved Late Asct. Prof. Dr. Aftab Hossain
&
Frontline COVID Heroes.

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study to evaluate the genomic and proteomic comparison between *Labeo rohita* of Halda River with *L. rohita* and other Indian major carps from other water bodies. In this study genetic and proteomic variation of *Labeo rohita* determined by functional genomics and proteomics through computational biology and bioinformatics. This is the advance level of consequent study which carried over the whole genome sequencing shotgun analysis done by the students of MS. Fisheries & Limnology Session 2017-2018 previous year. In chromosome level assembly of *L. rohita* total number of bases of the genome found is 1,159,574,983 . No. of sequence in my study is 2401 which indicates less fragmented better genome than other reference sequence. N50 is 35.5 mbp², L50 is smallest in my study 9, which is better because of having large sized scaffolds. Among 47,568 genes found in my study up to chromosome level, majority of those are placed in chromosome. Approximately 1010 annotated genes are protein coding and directly or indirectly responsible for muscle growth of *L. rohita* from Halda River. According to the refseq BAU-BD-2019 approximately 82 unique genes are found in *L. rohita* from Halda River. 29.27% of those genes are unplaced; 24 genes. Among 82 genes, 58 (70.73%) genes are placed in chromosome. Max. number of unique muscle genes lies in chr. 2 indicating high degree of polymorphism and mutations while no uniqueness in chr. 10, chr. 13, chr. 22 & chr. 23 indicates less polymorphism and mutations in those regions. This study carried out the divergence, unique genetic features of one of the most important common carp 'Rohu' from Halda River.

Table of Contents

Chapter	Biological Assessment	Page no.
	Acknowledgement	
	Abstract	
1	Introduction	01-39
	1.1 Preface	01
	1.2 Fish and Fisheries Resources of Bangladesh	01-04
	1.3 Location	04-09
	1.3.1 Halda River Research Laboratory (HRRL)	05
	1.3.2 Chittagong Veterinary And Animal Sciences University (CVASU)	06
	1.3.3. Map of the Study Area	07-09
	1.4 Aims and objectives	10
	1.5 Halda River: The natural genebank of carp fishes & Its unique features	10
	1.5.1 Fisheries Resources Of Halda River	10-12
	1.5.2 Natural breeding ground	12
	1.5.3 Halda as the natural breeding ground of Indian Major Carp	13-15
	1.6 Accounts Of <i>Labeo rohita</i>	15-26
	1.6.1 Morphological features of <i>Labeo rohita</i>	17
	1.6.2 Distribution	17
	1.6.3 Feeding Habit	18
	1.6.4 Breeding Behaviour	18
	1.6.5 Nutrition value of Rohu fish	19
	1.6.6 Current status of Rui fish in our country	19-26
	1.7 Background	27-39
	1.7.1 Importance of IMCs & Rohu Carp	29-30
	1.7.2 Gene & its structure	30-31
	1.7.2.1 Nucleotides	31-32
	1.7.2.2 Nucleic Acids	33-34
	1.7.2.3 Components of Nucleic Acids	34
	1.7.2.4 Genome & Proteome	34-35
	1.7.3 Importance of the genomic study	36-37
	1.7.4 Genome sequencing	37
	1.7.5 Whole Genome Sequencing	37-38
	1.7.6 Mitochondrial Genome Sequencing	38
	1.7.7 Databases of Biological Information	38-39
	1.7.7.1 DNA sequence databases	38
	1.7.7.2 Protein Directories	39
	1.7.8 Approaches in Bangladesh	39
2	Literature review	40-52

	2.1 Proteomic signature of muscle fibre hyperplasia	40
	2.2 Computational analysis of transcriptome of Indian major carps	40-41
	2.3 Expressed Sequences and Polymorphisms in Rohu Carp	41
	2.4 Identification of flesh-quality-attribute-related proteins	41-42
	2.5 Proteins related to flesh quality of fishes	42-43
	2.6 Muscle proteomics of Indian major carp <i>Catla catla</i>	43
	2.6.1 Partial gene sequences of gene coding	43
	2.7 Chromosome level assembly	43
	2.8 First phase of Genome Sequencing	44-45
	2.9 Genetic Approaches on Cultured Rohu	45-52
	2.9.1 Gene Cloning and Expression Profiling	45-51
	2.9.2 Marker Discovery with Whole-genome Sequencing	51-52
3	Materials and Methods	53-55
	3.1 Data collection	53
	3.2 Genome assembly	53
	3.3 Assembly quality assurance and benchmarking	53
	3.4 Functional genome analysis	53-54
	3.4.1 Repeat elements and divergent determination	54
	3.4.2 Gene prediction	54
	3.4.3 Protein prediction and annotation	54
	3.4.4 Quantitative trait loci analysis	54
	3.4.5 GWAS and Pathway analysis of economically important traits	54
	3.4.6 Data visualization	54
4	Results	56-69
	4.1 Chromosome level assembled genome	56-58
	4.2 Gene completeness benchmark	59-60
	4.3 Repeat elements on the genome	61
	4.4 Functional gene prediction and protein annotation	61
5	Comparative Analysis	70-87
	5.1 Comparative analysis of genome	70-75
	5.2 Comparative analysis of proteome	76-79
	5.3 Orthologs	80-87
6	Discussion	88-89
	6.1 Genome assembly & gene annotation	88
	6.2 Chromosome level assembly	88

	6.3 Comparative analysis of genome & proteome	88-89
7	Conclusion	90
8	References	91-95
	Appendices	96-153

Table No.	List of Tables	Page No.
01	Production of fisheries resources based on different fisheries sectors	04
02	List of Vulnerable, Endangered and Critically Endangered Species Found in Halda River (Azadi and Arshad-UI-Alam, 2013)	11
03	Egg collection records of Indian Major Carps (IMCs) from Halda River (Source: HRRL)	14
04	Nutrition value of Rohu fish	19
05	Total catch of Rohu from different water bodies in 2020-2021 (Source: DoF, 2021)	20
06	Total catch of Rohu from different rivers and basins in 2020-2021 (Source: DoF, 2021)	22
07	Total catch of Rohu from different water bodies of different districts in 2020-2021 (Source: DoF, 2021)	23-25
08	List of genes/transcripts cloned and characterized in Rohu with their biological functions (Rasal and Sundaray, 2020)	49-51
09	Genome statistics	56
10	BUSCO gene completeness benchmark	59
11	Number of genes per chromosome in my study	62
12	Showing summary of table for genomic data per chromosome	63
13	RefSeq BAU Genome Statistics	67
14	Chromosome wise gene distribution between my study and refseq	71
15	Chromosome wise non-coding and pseudogenes distribution between my study and refseq	74
16	Chromosome wise annotated gene protein distribution between my study and refseq	77
17	Proteins, clusters, singletons of Indian major carps, Kalibaus and Zebra fish	80
18	Chromosome wise unique genes of halda rohu (<i>L. rohita</i>)	86
19	Genes responsible for muscle growth of <i>L. rohita</i> from Halda River. (Bold names are expressing unique genes of halda rohu)	101

Figure No.	List of Figures	Page No.
01	Halda River Research Laboratory (HRRL)	05
02	Chittagong University & Animal Sciences University (CVASU) Campus	06
03	Location of Halda River (Source: Akter & Ali, 2012)	07
04	District map of Chittagong Division	08
05	Location of Halda River in Google Earth	09
06	Showing variations in collected amount of fish eggs in kg per year (2003-22)	15
07	Indian major carp <i>Labeo rohita</i> from Halda River	16
08	Labeled diagram of <i>Labeo rohita</i>	16
09	A School of young <i>L. rohita</i> in fish market	17
10	Slices of <i>L. rohita</i>	19
11	Graphical representation of production of <i>L. rohita</i> in different waterbodies	21
12	Graphical representation of total catch of Rohu from different divisions	26
13	Location of Gene within a cell	30
14	Diagram of Protein Synthesis, Central Dogma (Source: Encyclopedia Britannica)	31
15	Location of Gene within a cell (2)	32
16	Structural formula of purines & pyrimidines	32
17	Diagram of DNA & RNA	33
18	Detail ultrastructure of DNA & RNA	35
19	Pipeline of this comparative genome and proteome analysis with pathway	55
20	Comparison of total ungapped length among various studies	57
21	Comparison of number of sequences among various studies	57
22	Comparison of N50 among various studies	58
23	Comparison of L50 among various studies	58
24	Gene completeness with Class: Actinopterygii (Klein, 1885)	60
25	Gene completeness with Superkingdom: Eukaryota (Whittaker & Margulis, 1978)	60
26	Showing chromosome wise gene distribution (My study)	63
27	Annotated gene proteins and non-coding pseudogenes per chromosome	64

Figure No.	List of Figures	Page No.
28	Showing chromosome wise comparison between annotated proteins, non-coding & pseudogenes distribution among total genes	64
29	Annotated gene proteins and non-coding pseudogenes per chromosome among total genes	65
30	Visualization of Summary table for total genes, annotated proteins and non coding & pseudogenes	65
31	Extended Pie Diagram of placed & unplaced total genes, annotated proteins and non coding; pseudogenes	66
32	Visualization of genes, annotated proteins, gene ontology, KEGG pathway, Non-coding / Pseudogenes per chromosome	66
33	Showing chromosome wise gene distribution (refseq)	68
34	Showing chromosome wise comparison between annotated proteins, non-coding & pseudogenes distribution among total genes (refseq)	68
35	Annotated proteins & non-coding, pseudogenes per chromosome (Refseq)	69
36	Visualization of Summary table for total genes, annotated proteins and non coding & pseudogenes (refseq)	69
37	Comparison of genes per chromosome between my study & refseq	72
38	Comparison of genes per chromosome between my study & refseq with total no. of genes	72
39	Visualisation of Comparison between my study and refseq of total placed and unplaced genes along with total genes	73
40	Visualising comparison of non-coding and pseudogenes distribution between my study and refseq per chromosome	75
41	Visualisation of Comparison between my study and refseq of total placed and unplaced non-coding,pseudogenes along with summation	75
42	Comparison of proteins per chromosome between my study & refseq	78
43	Comparison of proteins per chromosome between my study & refseq with total no. of annotated genes/proteins	78
44	Visualising comparison of total annotated gene proteins distribution between my study and refseq	79
45	Ortholog cluster proteins among compared 5 species	81

Figure No.	List of Figures	Page No.
46	Ortholog cluster proteins (overlapped) among compared 5 species	82
47	Ortholog proteins among compared 5 species	83
48	Comparison of proteins, clusters and singletons in <i>Labeo rohita</i> from Halda River among other species	84
49	Ortho venn diagram indicating orthologs and unique protein clusters in <i>Labeo rohita</i> from Halda River among other species	85
50	Visualisation of chromosome wise unique genes of <i>Labeo rohita</i> from Halda River	87
51	Computational tools used in servers with CPU usage (tblastn, augustus)	96
52	Display showing genome statistics of reference genome	96
53	Computational tools used in servers with CPU usage (tblastn, augustus)	97
54	Gene prediction through AUGUSTUS	97
55	Running several tools & commands at a glance	98
56	Computational tools used in servers with CPU usage (tblastn, augustus)	98

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Preface

Bangladesh is a sovereign South Asian country. The country's marine territory in the Bay of Bengal is almost analogous to its land area, with territorial waters of 12 nautical miles, an EEZ of 200 nautical miles, and a continental shelf of 350 nautical miles from baseline.

The Bengal delta with numerous rivers characterizes the country's topography, while hilly regions and highlands make up the north-east and south-east regions.

Bangladesh is regarded as one of the world's most suitable fisheries locations, with the world's largest flooded wetland and Asia's third-highest aquatic biodiversity after China and India. It is located between 88°01E and 92°41E longitudes and 20°34N and 26°33N latitudes (Rashid, 1991). The nation covers an area of 147,570 square kilometers (56,980 square miles) (BBS 2020) and 148,460 square kilometers (57,320 square miles) (CIA World Factbook 2021), and it stretches 820 kilometers (510 miles) north to south and 600 kilometers (370 miles) east to west. Bangladesh's climate is tropical monsoonal, with considerable seasonal rainfall, hot temperatures, and significant humidity.

Bangladesh's once-rich fisheries resources may be attributed to enormous bodies of water such as rivers, floodplains, beels, baors, or oxbow lakes; the Kaptai reservoir; man-made ponds; estuaries with a wide range of salinity gradients; and marine waterways (GOB and IUCN, 2015).

1.2 Fish and Fisheries resources of Bangladesh

Bangladesh's excellent geographic location results in a huge number of aquatic species and lots of resources to sustain its fisheries potential. Bangladesh has enormous fishing and aquaculture potential because of its abundant interior lakes and river systems. In the national cuisine, fish is a favorite accompaniment to rice, giving birth to the saying "A Bengali is formed of fish and rice" (Ghose, 2014). Bangladesh's various water ecosystems sustain a broad range of fish. The total number of freshwater fish species found in Bangladesh ranges from 250 to 266. (Rahman 2005, Siddiqui et al. 2007). A conservative estimate puts the overall number of species at 260. However, a number more species have since been added to the list (Ahmed et al. 2013, Singer and Page 2015, Kullander et al. 2015). It is estimated that just a few freshwater fish species remain unknown in Bangladesh. However, all of the freshwater species listed are not exclusively freshwater; in estuaries as many as 62 species are found, and a number of them comes from the Bay of Bengal and rise through tidal rivers (Rahman 2005, Siddiqui et al. 2007). 104 of the recorded species are riverine, 36 are migratory (crossing rivers and floodplains), and the additional 113 are floodplain resident species (FAP 17 1995). Riverine species breed on rivers,

migratory species breed in rivers but migrate between rivers and floodplains during the flood season, and floodplain resident individuals breed and feed in floodplains but may seek refuge in rivers during the dry season. Furthermore, 20 species of prawns, 4 species of crabs, and 26 species of molluscs have been identified in Bangladesh's freshwaters (Ahmed and Ali 1996, Siddiqui et al. 2008a and 2008b). There are several freshwater species of fish found in hill streams that are uncommon in other aquatic habitats. Hill stream fishes have evolved to thrive in fast-flowing rivers with sandy and pebbly substrates. Moreover, up to 24 exotic species are discovered in freshwater aquaculture (Hossain 2014), some of which infrequently escape into open waterways but have yet to establish in inland open waters. Fish and fisheries play a key role in Bangladesh's nutrition, economics, employment, and heritage. In contrast, fish is Bangladesh's second most important food after rice. It is the world's third largest producer of freshwater fish (FAO 2022, IUCN 2015)

In Bangladesh, 1.2 million professional fishermen work full-time to support their families, while additional 10 million fishers indulge in subsistence fishing to supplement their incomes or for family use. In essence, every household in rural Bangladesh engages in some form of fishing (DoF 2014). Reduction in fish supply in the country will have an adverse effect on the nutrition, employment, and livelihood of many people (IUCN 2015).

The fisheries are roughly divided into three categories: inland capture, inland aquaculture, and marine fisheries, with the inland aquaculture sector accounting for more than 57.1%, inland open water capture comprises 28.2% summed up 85.3% and marine fisheries contribute about 14.7% of total fish production (DoF, 2022). The fisheries sector plays a very important role in the national economy, contributing 3.52% to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the country and 26.37% to the agricultural GDP (DoF, 2022). From 2004-05 to 2013-14 FY, the fisheries growth was fairly steady and at an average of 5.38% per year and over the last 8 years (2014-15 to 2021-22 FY), the growth faced ups and downs at an average of 3.80% per year (FRSS 2015, BER 2022). This sector experienced a more or less consistent growth rate, ranging from 7.32% growth in 2009-2010 to 2.62% growth in 2020-21, (BER 2014, BER 2022). In FY 2021-22, the fisheries profession's GDP growth rate is 2.08 percent, and its contribution to the entire agriculture sector is 21.83 percent. The government is undertaking a number of initiatives to increase fish output in order to assure a continuous source of animal protein. Fish farming in open water, endangered fish species conservation, the creation of fish breeding and breeding sanctuaries, the protection of Jatka, efficient and environmentally friendly shrimp farming, and other initiatives are now happening. The Halda River, a natural fish spawning hub, has been designated as a 'Bangabandhu Fisheries Heritage' site. The production of fish in the fiscal year 2020-21 has been about 4,621,228 metric tons which is 117858 metric tons more than that of the previous year 2019-20 showing growth rate of 2.62% (FRSS 2020-21, FRSS 2019-20, BER,2022).

In 2001-02, the total production of fish in the country was 1,890,459 metric tons (DoF 2001-02). Due to the implementation of various fishery-friendly activities of the government, fish production has more than doubled in the last 2 decades. From 2001-02 to 2020-21, we have seen a 244% growth in fish production in our country (DoF 2001-02, FRSS 2019-20, FRSS 2020-21, BER 2022).

Fisheries sector contributes 3.57 percent of the country's total GDP, 26.50 percent of the agricultural GDP and 1.24 percent of the total export earnings. About 2 crore people of the country, which is more than 12 percent of the total population, are directly or indirectly involved in various activities of the fisheries sector.

More than 2% of Bangladeshi export value comes from the inland fisheries sector. Given proper government support, the fisheries sector has ample potential in creating various types of ancillary industries in rural areas that often have a high rate of economic return.

It has one of the biggest and most active deltas, fed by three mighty Padma the Meghna and the Jamuna. This contributes to a high potential for fresh and brackish water capture and culture fisheries, in addition to the vast marine resources.

Despite Bangladesh's long coastline and large freshwater and marine water bodies, fisheries are underdeveloped compared to other industry sectors. Inland fisheries production has escalated over the years, but the productivity per hectare water area is not yet attained at its optimum. In recent years, the bulk of the production has been obtained from marine (16.78%) and freshwater (83.22%) wild capture fisheries. In 2015-2016, Bangladesh was the 5th in world aquaculture production, which accounted for half of the country's total fish production (55.15%). In 2014-2015, total fishery production of Bangladesh was 3,684,245 metric tons, of which 1,023,991 metric tons was obtained from inland capture fisheries, 2,060,408 metric tons from inland aquaculture and 599,846 metric tons from marine water production (FRSS, 2016). In 2020-2021, total fisheries production increased to 4,621,228 metric tons, where 1,301,244 metric tons collected from inland capture fisheries, 2,638,745 metric tons from inland aquaculture and 6,81,239 metric tons from marine water production (DoF, 2022). There have been few reviews of the development and potential of fisheries and aquaculture in many parts of Bangladesh published.

The extent of different types of water bodies & fisheries resources are as follows:
(According to Yearbook of Fisheries Statistics of Bangladesh, FRSS 2020-21)

Table 01. Production of fisheries resources based on different fisheries sectors

Type of fisheries	Fisheries Sector	Water Area (Ha)	Productions (MT)
Inland fisheries	Inland open water (capture): Rivers, Estuary, Sundarbans, Beel, Kaptai lake, Floodplain	3,860,466	1,301,244
	Inland closed water (culture): Pond, Seasonal cultured water body, Baor, Shrimp/Prawn, Farm, Pen culture, Cage culture	8,43,729	2,638,745
	Total	4,704,195	3,939,989
Marine Fisheries	Industrial Trawl fishing	12,111,000	1,19,121
	Artisenal fishing		5,62,118
	Total		6,81,239
	Grand Total	16,815,195	4,621,228

The fresh water bodies harbor more or less 266 species of fish and a total of 13 species of cultural finfish have been introduced in Bangladesh since the very beginning of 1952 with the target of accelerating production and limiting weeds and insects (IUCN Bangladesh, 2000). Bangladesh is a river based agricultural country. The fisheries resources provides full time employment to an estimated 2.5 million people and an estimated around 75% of the rural chores taken over by some kind of fishing activity. Hence, the fisheries sector plays an important role in the socio-economic life of our country.

1.3 Location

Bangladesh is blessed with a vast expanse of inland open waters and rivers, canals, natural and man-made lakes, freshwater marshes, estuaries, brackish water impoundments and floodplains. This research focuses on one of the IMCs of Halda River. This entire research was carried out in two different locations of Chittagong, Bangladesh. The first location is Halda River Research Laboratory, University of Chittagong. The second location is Chattogram Veterinary and Animal Sciences University (CVASU) where Computational tasks were done in the server room.

1.3.1 Halda River Research Laboratory (HRRL)

HRRL (22°46'77.39" N, 91°77'80.79" E) is a specialized research laboratory of the University of Chittagong, Hathazari that checks river health by focusing on physical, chemical, and biological characteristics of the environment and river ecosystems. This laboratory preserves the resources, history, culture, and heritage of the Halda River, as well as contributes to the development of Halda River's indigenous technology of egg collection of IMCs.

Figure 01. Halda River Research Laboratory (HRRL)

1.3.2 Chittagong Veterinary and Animal Sciences University (CVASU)

CVASU (22°36'27.629" N, 91°80'21.417" E) is the most populous and renowned specialized university for veterinary and animal sciences study which is situated at Khulshi, Chattogram. It has campuses also in Hathazari, Chattogram, Purbachal, Dhaka and Dariyanagar, Cox's Bazar. Genomic DNA extraction and computational analysis of raw reads sequence data were carried out in the Pathology laboratory of CVASU and Next-Gen Informatics Ltd. of this University for the research purpose which our antecedent seniors did on this topic.

Figure 02. Chittagong University & Animal Sciences University (CVASU) Campus

1.3.3. Map of the Study Area

Figure 03. Location of Halda River (Source: Akter & Ali, 2012)

Figure 04. District map of Chittagong.Division

Figure 05. Location of Halda River in Google Earth.

1.4 Aims and objectives

- ⊖ to determine the genetic variation of *Labeo rohita* through functional genomics.
- ⊖ to identify marker genes for branding of *Labeo rohita* from the Halda River.
- ⊖ to explore unique genetic features of Halda fishes.

1.5 Halda River: The natural genebank of carp fishes & Its unique features

Due to some unique and rare features, Halda River is recognised as a very unique river of Bangladesh. Halda river is the only endemic river of our country, which starts and ends in Bangladesh. It is the natural habitat of four major carps (*L. rohita*, *Catla catla*, *C. cirrhosis* and *L. calbasu*) (Podder et al., 2017; Tsai et al., 1981) and also the home of the Gangetic River Dolphin, *Platanista gangetica* (Smith et al., 2001; IUCN, 2015). The most important feature is the collecting procedure of fertilized eggs of IMCs directly from the river. Halda river provides livelihood for hundreds of people who solely utilize its natural resources. The riverine area's locality has developed its own culture and lifestyle depending on the river (Kabir et al., 2013). It is considered as a lifeline for Chattogram city as Halda River fulfills the water requirement for this heavily populated city. To emphasize its importance and to preserve the aquatic resources of this river, the Bangladesh government designated this river as "Bangabondhu Fisheries Heritage" in December, 2020. As it is the only endemic river, rest of all originated from India or Myanmar. So, the people of Chattogram desire that one day Halda will be designated as "National River" of our country.

1.5.1 Fisheries Resources of Halda River

The variety of life forms and the ecosystems that make up the freshwater, tidal, and marine regions of the world and their interactions are all together concluded as aquatic biodiversity. Economic and aesthetic value of aquatic resources of any country plays a very crucial role in maintaining and conserving the environmental health of that particular habitat. Before the dawn of civilization, humans have long been dependent on these aquatic resources. Most of the civilized colonies were founded near rivers or places where water resources were easily accessible. Other than commercial purposes aquatic resources play a vital role in transportation and also recreational activities. A well maintained aquatic habitat with great diversity ensures the availability of food resources and safe breeding ground for species of that particular habitat. However, these aquatic environments can face serious damage due to overexploitation of species, toxic pollution from urban areas, industrial and agricultural pollution. Damming, water diversion, and habitat loss are the other reasons that threaten the diversity of aquatic species, making them vulnerable and susceptible to extinction.

Bangladesh is endowed with surface and ground water resources. Padma, Meghna, Jamuna and Brahmaputra and their numerous tributaries crisscrossing over this evergreen beautiful land making a netting system. Though Halda is an important river

of Bangladesh, the aquatic biodiversity of this river has not been described statistically yet (Chowdhury et al., 2011). But recently researchers are attempting to document the species diversity of Halda River, realizing its importance in national economy and public health. Attempts have been declared and enacted to conserve its biodiversity. With this regard, Azadi and colleagues enlisted a total of 83 finfish species under 13 orders and 35 families and a total of 10 shellfish (9 prawns and 1 crab) under 1 order and 3 families from the Halda River which took seven years to complete (from September 2004 to December 2011 (Azadi and Alam, 2013) Cyprinidae formed the dominant group among the fin fishes with 19 species while Gobiidae was the second largest group with 11 species. Three exotic species *Aristichthys nobilis*, *Hypophthalmichthys molitric* and *Oreochromis niloticus* were recorded from Halda River According to their study 3 critically endangered, 8 vulnerable and 9 endangered species were recorded (Table 1). Among IMCs, *L. calabasu* was recorded as an endangered species. Halda River is unique due to its egg collection procedure of IMCs. So, if any of its IMCs face the threat of extinction, it can be assumed that without proper management, these four valuable species along with other economically important fish species can face the threat of extinction in near future. Thus, the importance of preserving genetic features of these pure wild breeds of IMCs should be one of our national concerns.

Table 02. List of Vulnerable, Endangered and Critically Endangered Species Found in Halda River (Azadi and Arshad-UI-Alam, 2013).

* **Vulnerable species**

** **Endangered Species**

*** **Critically Endangered Species**

Serial No.	Family Name	Species	Local Name
01.	Anguillidae	<i>Anguilla bengalensis</i> *	Boro Bain
02.	Cyprinidae	<i>Labeo calabasu</i> *	Kalibaus
		<i>L. gonius</i> **	Ghonia
		<i>Osteobrama cotio</i> **	Lohachura
		<i>Chela laubuca</i> **	Deshi Laubuca
		<i>Crossocheilus latius</i> **	Kalo Bata

		<i>Puntius ticto</i> *	Tit Puti
		<i>Rasbora rasbora</i> **	Darkina
		<i>Sperata aor</i> *	Aair
03.	Bagridae	<i>Mystus cavasius</i> *	Gangeo Tengra
04.	Pangasiidae	<i>Pangasius pangasius</i> ***	Pangash
05.	Notopteridae	<i>Notopterus notopterus</i> *	Foli
06.	Schilbeidae	<i>Clupisoma garua</i> ***	Garua Bacha
07.	Siluridae	<i>Ompok pabda</i> **	Pabda
08.	Ambassidae	<i>Chanda nama</i> *	Nama Chanda
		<i>Parambassis ranga</i> *	Ranga Chanda
09.	Scatophagidae	<i>Scatophagus argus</i> **	Bishtara
10.	Channidae	<i>Channa orientalis</i> *	Telotaki/Cheng
11.	Mastacembelidae	<i>Mastacembelus armatus</i> **	Shal Baim

1.5.2. Natural breeding ground

Instinct breeding of fishes in a natural environment is known as natural fish breeding. Naturally in the favorable environment of the tide stream, heavy rainfall, thunderstorm, low water temperature, high air moisture, water whirlpool, and several other factors which influence a hormone of fish inside their body named Gonadotropin Hormone (GTH) reached to reproductive organ through blood and incite the fish for breeding (Azadi and Alam, 2013). The breeding period of most of the fishes is May to August. For natural propagation, males and females are placed together in a breeding area such as a small pond or an enclosure where they spawn naturally. This method is usually used, for example, to produce tilapias in mass amounts which makes it cheap in the fish market (Ali et al., 2010).

1.5.3. Halda as the natural breeding ground of Indian Major Carp

Halda River has a great impact since it is a natural breeding ground of Indian major carp fishes. It is also a vast source of naturally occurring Indian major carp (Bhuiyan et al., 2018). Several species of fish and other freshwater fish species usually breed in the Halda River (Tsai et al., 1981). This river is the one and the only natural carp breeding ground in Bangladesh from where fertilized carp fish's (*Catla catla*, *Labeo rohita*, *Labeo calbasu* and *Cirrhinus cirrhosus*) eggs are collected by local fisherman and egg collectors during April to June almost every year for time immemorial (Ali et al., 2010). The collected eggs are hatched in the artificial mud-made scoop on the riverbank to produce carp fries. The fry from here are supplied to different regions of the country for aquaculture (Bhuiyan et al., 2019).

To correctly compare and assess the status of Indian Major Carp brood fishes and fish population in the Halda river it is very much important to record the egg collection data over the years. Halda River Research Laboratory analyzed the egg collection data for the last 20 years. Among all of those years no egg spawning was recorded in the year 2004 and in 2016 only 735 kg eggs were collected. Among several factors brood fish killing and trapping is one of the most common causes responsible for the decline in egg production. After several laws and management programmes were taken by government and NGO's to preserve the brood fishes, in 2020 the amount of eggs collected broke the record of the previous 14 years. with 25,600 kg of eggs. However in 2021 this decreased to 8,500 kg and then this year further subsided to 3,500 kg of eggs. Such fluctuation in the spawning behavior is due to environmental conditions which degraded due to anthropogenic activities. In 2022 less rainfall, effect of short monsoon causes the lower amount of egg production by major carps.

Table 03. Egg collection records of Indian Major Carps (IMCs) from Halda River (Source: HRRL)

Year	Amount of collected eggs (Kg)
2003	13,020
2004	00
2005	22,314
2006	2,400
2007	13,200
2008	9,000
2009	12,600
2010	9,000
2011	12,600
2012	21,240
2013	4,200
2014	16,500
2015	2,800
2016	735
2017	1,680
2018	22,680
2019	9,000

Year	Amount of collected eggs (Kg)
2020	25,600
2021	8,500
2022	3,500

Figure 06. Showing variations in collected amount of fish eggs in kg per year (2003-22) (Source : HRRL)

1.6 Accounts of *Labeo rohita*

Otophysi, a clade of modern freshwater fishes. Superorder Otophysi is currently classified into four orders: Cypriniformes (Carp and minnows; 4262 species), Characiformes (~2100 species), Gymnotiformes (225 species) and Siluriformes (~3700 species) (Eschmeyer and Fong, 2015; Nelson et al. , 2016). *Labeo rohita* is a member of family Cypriniformes.

Common name : Rohu

Local Bengali name : Rui, Ruit, Rou, Rohu

Systematic position:

Phylum: Chordata

Class: Osteichthyes

Order: Cypriniformes

Family: Cyprinidae

Sub family: Cyprininae

Genus: *Labeo* (Cuvier, 1817)

Species: *L. rohita*

Scientific name: *Labeo rohita* (Hamilton, 1822)

Figure 07. Indian major carp *Labeo rohita* from halda river

Figure 08. Labeled diagram of *Labeo rohita*

1.6.1 Morphological features of *Labeo rohita*

The dorso-lateral portion of the body of rohu is brownish and on the sides and under its body is mainly silvery. Fins are grey, dark and dusky in colour and pectoral fins are observed. Both lips are covered by black cartilaginous covering. A pair of short maxillary barbells is present. Dorsal and abdominal profiles are convex and the caudal peduncle is short. The complete lateral line is observed.

Fin formula: D. 15-16 (3/12-13), P1.16-17, P2. 9. A. 7(2/5) (Rahman, 2005).

This means *Labeo rohita* has a dorsal fin (D) with 3 spines and 13 soft rays, pectoral fin (P1) with 16-17 soft rays, pelvic fin (P2) with 9 soft rays and anal fin (A) with total 7 rays where 2 spines and 5 soft rays lies.

L. rohita is column feeder at mid-water and prefers to feed on plant matters including decaying vegetation (Jhingram and Pullin, 1985). Its food comprises crustaceous and insect larvae in the early stages (Mookerjee et al., 1946).

1.6.2 Distribution

Rohu is a natural inhabitant of the freshwater section of Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, Burma and Terai region of Nepal and also has been transplanted into Sri Lanka, Japan, Philippines, Malaysia and some countries of Africa (Jhingram and Pullin, 1985). In Bangladesh, Rohu is mostly found in the Padma-Brahmaputra, their tributaries and Halda river system (Alam et al., 2009), though Halda is the only river in Bangladesh from where fertilized eggs of major carps are collected (Tsai et al., 1981; Patra and Azadi, 1985).

Figure 09. A School of young *L. rohita* in fish market

1.6.3 Feeding Habit

In the natural habitat, the food and feeding habits of Rohu are unknown. Some authors regard Rohu to be a water column feeder (Dewan et al., 1991, Wahab et al., 1994, Azim et al., 2004), many consider it to be a surface feeder (Hora, 1944), while others consider it as both surface and column feeder (Das and Moitra, 1955). Though its food is comprises of crustaceans and insect larvae in the early stages (Mookerjee et al., 1946). These conclusions were mostly based on gut content analysis and not on behavioral observations.

1.6.4 Breeding Behaviour

Rohu fish is a species that likes to grow in moving water, mainly rivers. In the midst of its second year in the river, Rohu fish reaches full growth. The southwest monsoon usually coincides with Rohu's spawning season In flooded rivers, the eggs are laid. In general, carps lay their eggs when the following important factors are fulfilled (Tsai et al., 1981)

1. The tide should be at its highest level.
2. There must be heavy floodwater runoff from the hilly region.
3. There should be a sharp increase in water level, turbidity and current velocity.

There should be a decrease in temperature, dissolved oxygen and hydrogen ion concentration.

The fecundity of this species varies from 2,26,000 to 2,79,4000 depending upon the length and weight (Talwar and Jhingran, 1991)

Figure 10. Slices of *L. rohita*

Table 04. Nutrition value of Rohu fish

Nutrients	Amount Present	% of daily intake (Based on 2000 calories)
Protein	23 gm	59%
Fat	7 gm	41%
Sodium	23 mg	3%
Good Cholesterol	84 mg	28%
Omega 3 Fatty Acids	Present	Adequate
Total Energy	162 calories	8.1%

In per slice (100gm) of serving (myfitnesspal.com)

1.6.6 Current status of Rui fish of our country

Rui fish is one of the most common major carp in our country. It is the most valuable major carp on the basis of its economic importance. Based on total catch we can understand the present condition of Rui fish and its availability in our country. Rui fish constitutes a large portion in the freshwater fish group. According to Yearbook of Fisheries Statistics of Bangladesh 2020-2021, It can be said that Rui is more or less leading caught fish in 2020-2021 in inland open water fisheries i.e. River &

estuaries, Sundarbans, Beel, Kaptai Lake & Flood-plain also in inland closed water fisheries i.e. pond, seasonal cultured waterbody, baor etc. In annual fish production 2020-21 major carps constitutes 21.11% of total captured fishes which is 9,75,531 metric ton among 46,21,228 metric ton of total fish catch. Major carps indicates mainly Rui, Catla & Mrigel (YFSB 2020-21).

Table 05. Total catch of Rohu from different water bodies in 2020-2021 (Source: DoF, 2021)

Types of Waterbodies	Amount of Catch (mt)
River	3231
Beel	13558
Kaptai Lake	09
Flood Plain	46441
Pond	294837
Seasonal Cultured Water Body	53099
Baor	1626
Shrimp/Prawn Farm	31374
Pen Culture	1968
Total	446143

CATCH RATIO OF RUI BASED ON DIFFERENT SECTORS

Types of Waterbodies

Figure 11. Graphical representation of production of *L. rohita* in different waterbodies

Table 06. Total catch of Rohu from different rivers and basins in 2020-2021 (Source: DoF, 2021)

Rivers & basins	Amount of catch (mt)
Lower Meghna	177
Upper Meghna	272
Lower Padma	260
Upper Padma	228
Jamuna	197
Brahmaputra	199
Total Principal Rivers	1333
Other Rivers	1898
Total	3231

Table 07. Total catch of Rohu from different water bodies of different districts in 2020-2021 (Source: DoF, 2021)

Name of Districts	Divisions	Amount of catch (mt)
Dhaka	Dhaka	43
Faridpur		24
Gazipur		15
Gopalganj		44
Shariatpur		19
Rajbari		26
Madaripur		14
Manikganj		11
Munshiganj		12
Kishoreganj		60
Narsingdi		13
Tangail		12
Sub-total		
Mymensingh	Mymensingh	38
Jalalpur		21
Netrokona		31
Sherpur		82

Sub-total		172
Chuadanga	Khulna	17
Jashore		28
Kushtia		50
Magura		82
Meherpur		03
Narail		50
Sub-total		230
Gaibandha		Rangpur
Kurigram	13	
Lalmonirhat	11	
Nilphamari	06	
Rangpur	12	
Sub-total	92	
Bogura	Rajshahi	52
Chapai Nawabganj		82
Joypurhat		42
Naogaon		112
Natore		91
Pabna		120
Rajshahi		76

Sirajganj		105
Sub-total		680
Bandarban	Chattogram	07
Brahmanbaria		59
Chandpur		59
Chattogram		04
Cumilla		70
Feni		58
Lakshmipur		03
Noakhali		03
Rangamati		06
Sub-total		269
Habiganj		Sylhet
Moulvibazar	15	
Sunamganj	46	
Sylhet	59	
Sub-total	156	
Grand Total	7 Divisions	1892

Figure 12. Graphical representation of total catch of Rohu from different divisions

1.7 Background

In Bangladesh, *Labeo rohita*, locally known as Rui, in the global arena known as “ROHU” contributed 10.55% of the total annual fish production of inland water bodies, which is far greater than the other three major carps of Bangladesh viz. Catla (6.46%), Mrigal (6.50%) and Kalibaus (1.05%) (DoF, 2019). Rohu, is an important Indian major carp (IMC) that thrives as a prime species in aquaculture practice among the other three major carps available in Bangladesh. Among all IMCs, Rohu supplies the highest percentage of protein and acts as a Calcium and Vitamin-A source (Ahmed et al., 2012; Roos et al., 2002).

On the other hand, Halda River is considered to be the natural breeding ground for Rohu and the only river from where fertilized eggs of Rohu are collected (Isai et al., 1981; Patra and Azadi, 1985). Quality of eggs, fry and fingerling collected from this natural source are far greater than those of induced breeding and highly favored in aquaculture practice. Halda's fingerlings are sold out around 1,00,000 Tk/Kg where fingerlings produced in hatcheries are sold at around 5,000 to 10,000 Tk/Kg or even less. The market value of naturally produced Rohu and farmed Rohu also varied greatly as consumers can detect the distinguishable taste and quality between them.

Bangladesh is one of the world's leading fish producing countries where aquaculture production contributes 56.76% of the total fish production with 43.84 lakh MT of fish and fishery products. Also, the fisheries sector contributed 3.50% to the national GDP and more than 25.72% to the agricultural GDP. Most importantly over 12% of the 165 million people of Bangladesh depend on fisheries and aquaculture related sectors for their livelihood (DoF, 2019). Bangladesh ranked 3rd in inland open water capture production and by contributing approximately 2.93% it ranked 5th in world aquaculture production (FAO, 2018). In order to meet the protein requirement of the increasing population, aquaculture has been expanding in Bangladesh during the last twenty-five years and currently, 50% of the total fish production comes from aquaculture (FRSS, 2012). With this food security, aquaculture is gaining popularity in Bangladesh, fish seed demand in private and public hatcheries is also increasing. Major carps are popular in aquaculture due to their fast-growing nature and also they can be cultured with other fish in the fish polyculture system. IMCs attain maturity at a certain age but do not spawn naturally in the confined farm environment. However, spawning can be achieved using a scientific strategy that involves developing natural requirements in artificial farms. Thus, induced spawning came into the picture to complement this ongoing seed requirement. Scientists have been addressing issues like inbreeding depressions, deterioration of brood stock quality, lack of scientific approach in broodstock selection and management in induced farming of major carps. This is because there is a growing concern that hatchery stocks may be severely inbred. The overall performance of hatchery stocks is rapidly deteriorating since all hatcheries function as isolated genetically closed units by raising their own stock of breeders and producing fish seed from them to distribute grow-out areas (Eknath, et

al., 1990). It does not matter whether cognizant artificial selection for genetic enhancement is practiced or not but accumulation of genetic effects from generation to generation is already prevailing in our aquaculture practice which will eventually lead to permanent changes in broodstock quality. Therefore, a careful analysis and designing of management practices to control these selection forces is necessary to maximize the genetic potentiality of the culture stock (Doyle, 1983; Gall, 1983). To address this issue scientists have been conducting research for several years. From previous knowledge, it is visible that poor management of brood stock and lack of scientific approach in those fish farms can lead to gene loss which is a common scenario in Bangladesh (Simonsen et al., 2005; Rahman et al., 2009). Thus, gene pools of our indigenous varieties of carps viz: Rohu, Catla & Mrigal have been contaminated (Khatun et al., 2017).

Halda is the only river from where fertilized eggs of these major carps are collected and kept for stocking and kept for hatching.

Recently this river and its aquatic habitat is facing threat due to human origin activities and natural calamities and disasters. Along with ecological disturbance in Halda River, the annual collection of fertilized eggs of these IMCs is showing a declining trend. It clearly proves the risk of those species in their natural habitat. Also, the natural populations are showing a declining trend due to habitat loss. The threats to the fish are in general but as the fish is cultured nationwide thus the fish is assessed as least concern (IUCN, 2015).

Bangladesh is a riverine delta in the Indian basin, as she has more or less 700 river with a very strong extensive network of five river system. She has a river system network across the whole country, it supports in the extensive growth of fish production. River based fish production helps in growth of fisheries sector exponentially. This sector contributes 3.50% to the national GDP and 25.72% to the total agricultural GDP of the country (BER, 2019). Last 12 years the average growth performance of this sector is 5.01%. More or less 12% of people are directly or indirectly involved in various activities under the fisheries sector for their livelihood. Bangladesh achieved self-sufficiency in fish production with a per capita fish consumption of 62.58 g/day against a set target of 60 g/day (BBS, 2016).

Labeo rohita is one of the major carp that intended and commonly found on the water body of Bangladesh. This cyprinid fish is called as "RUI" across our country. As it has a vast influence over the fisheries sector which indirectly contribute to our economic advancement as fisheries sector flourishes. In our riverine country, Halda is the only river where carp brood fishes reproduce naturally. Halda River rises from the Badnatali Hill Ranges in the Chattogram Hill Tracts range at latitude 22°38'00" N and longitude 92°10'00" E, enters Chattogram district through Fatikchhari upazilla. Then it flows southwest keeping off the higher regions to the north and then due south past Bibirhat, Nazirhat, Sattarghat, Fatikchhari, Hathzari, Raozan

and Kotwali. Kalurghat where it falls into the Karnafully River at latitude 22°25'13" N and longitude 91°52'33" E.(Mohammad Shahidul Alam, SifatulQuader Chowdhury).Halda has its own unique properties and ecosystem which integrate the all demands needed for the spawning of brood fishes. Alongside all the carp fishes, 'Rohu' is one of the major carp found on Halda river. Growth of 'Rohu' in halda river is often seen very much faster than the other rivers and also closed water farms.As we have seen Rohu of halda grown upto 10-15kg very quickly.Muscles of halda river Rohu are also smoother and fleshy than other farm and river fishes. Its good taste and high market price makes it one of the favorite freshwater aquaculture fish in Bangladesh. In Bangladesh among the four Indian major carp species, (*Labeo rohita*, *Catla catla*, *Cyprinus carpio* and *Cirrhinus cirrhosus*) Rohu ensures the top position of consumer preference due to its good test, quality, reasonable price and availability and also in the national economy, the contribution of Rohu is beyond question. *L. rohita* is widely distributed in the country. The natural populations show a declining trend due to habitat loss. The fish is extensively cultured in the country and is used in floodplain programmes. The threats to the fish are in general. Hence, the fish is assessed as Least Concern (IUCN., 2015).

1.7.1 Importance of IMCs & Rohu Carp

Indian Major Carps constitute a very large group of freshwater fish, predominant in the aquaculture system and accounting for approximately 71% to 75% of freshwater fish production (FAO, 2018). The largest producer of carp is China (78.7%), followed by India (15.7%); the remaining 10.2% is produced by Bangladesh, Myanmar, Vietnam, Indonesia and Pakistan collectively, contributing more than 30% of global aquaculture production in terms of tons (FAO, 2017). *L. rohita* currently accounts for around 3.7% of total freshwater aquaculture production worldwide (FAO, 2018). Fish polyculture is common in aquaculture history of Bangladesh and Rohu is cultured with other major carps. In 2017-2018, major carp contributed 19.79% in total fish production of Bangladesh, of which Rohu alone accounts for 10.60% of total major carp production (DoF, 2018). According to their study, Rohu is the most common and popular among IMCS which is confirmed by its larger production rate. From natural water bodies, total catch is extremely low. In 2018-2019 total catch of rohu fish are as follows, 168 and 256 catch from upper and lower Meghna respectively, 246 and 217 from lower and upper Padma respectively, from Jamuna & Brahmaputra 188 and 197 catch accordingly. This analysis reflects that habitat of Rohu population is degrading. The total production of Rohu in inland capture and culture fisheries mainly indicates the population decreasing situation of wild and pure rohu in an alarming rate.

Figure 13. Location of Gene within a cell

1.7.2 Gene & its Structure

Genes are a large set of polynucleotide chains, composed of helical or non helical structure bonded by hydrogen bond, peptide bond, glycosidic bond etc. Those chains lie in the chromatin fibre of the nucleus of a cell. Polynucleotides are mainly bonded with histone and non histone proteins to form chromatin fibre. Polynucleotide is mainly made of bonding between single nucleotides. Gene is considered the basic unit of inheritance, as it contains a large set of data of organisms which is used to solve the unsolved mysterious function and structure of cells. Genes are passed from parents to its offspring which bear the information needed to specify physical and biological traits. A set of genes contains a distinctive region that acts in its own certain manner. Most genes code for distinct proteins which have differing functions within the body. i.e. Humans have approximately 20,000 protein coding genes. A set of genes usually composed of promoting sequence, coding sequence, non coding sequence and terminating sequence. Promoting sequence promotes the conversion of the language of genes to simpler forms of genetic materials, mainly messenger RNA (mRNA). Then mRNA translates its data to the form of amino acids which further

create proteins. This complex process is known as protein synthesis, which is held by three consecutive processes: replication, transcription and translation.

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Figure 14. Diagram of Protein Synthesis, Central Dogma (Source: Encyclopedia Britannica)

1.7.2.1 Nucleotides

Nucleotides are the basic building blocks of our lively earth composed of nucleosides and phosphoric acid. Nucleosides are made of pentose sugar (C_5) & Nitrogenous base. When nucleosides get attached to their adjacent phosphoric acid then it's called nucleotides. There are two types of pentose sugar, ribose sugar and deoxyribose sugar. When ribose sugar ($C_5H_{10}O_5$) releases an oxygen molecule from its 2' Carbon then it turns into deoxyribose ($C_5H_{10}O_4$). Nitrogenous bases are mainly of two types, purine and pyrimidine. Purines and pyrimidines make up the bases in both RNA and DNA. The two common purines are adenine (A) and guanine (G). Purine structure consists of two adjoining rings with five carbons and four nitrogens. The common pyrimidines are cytosine (C), thymine (T), and uracil (U). Pyrimidines have one ring with four carbons and two nitrogens. The structures are shown in Figure 03. Nucleic acids are large biomolecules that play essential roles in all cells and also in viruses. Phosphate groups are added with 5' Carbon of the pentose sugar ribose or deoxyribose. Thus ribonucleotide and deoxyribonucleotide are created. Some ribonucleotides i.e. Adenosine Triphosphate (ATP), Cytidine Di-phosphate (CDP), Uridine mono-phosphate (UMP), some deoxyribonucleotides i.e. Deoxyguanosine mono-phosphate (dGMP), Deoxythymidine triphosphate (dTTP).

Figure 15. Location of Gene within a cell (2)

Figure 16. Structural formula of purines & pyrimidines

1.7.2.2 Nucleic Acids

Nucleotides are attached with each other through phospho di-ester bonds between 3' carbon of pentose sugar and 5' carbon of its adjacent nucleotides. Thus a long chain of nucleotides is created known as the polynucleotide chain. Two polynucleotide chains attach with each other via hydrogen bonds between antithetic confront nitrogenous bases. Which results in double helical structure of DNA. There are mainly two types of nucleic acid based on their pentose sugar backbone. Those are 'Ribonucleic acid' and 'Deoxyribonucleic acid', acronyms respectively RNA and DNA. Whole or partial portions of RNA or DNA act as genes which further carry genetic traits to the offspring. Major function of nucleic acids involves the storage and expression of genomic information. Deoxyribonucleic acid, or DNA, encodes the information cells need to make proteins. A related type of nucleic acid, called ribonucleic acid (RNA), comes in different molecular forms that play multiple cellular roles, including protein synthesis.

Figure 17. Diagram of DNA & RNA

Genes or DNA replicated or copied through long complex reactions caused by several replication factors and enzymes. Division of cells which completely rely on karyokinesis, mainly lies on the DNA replication. Because nuclear materials are only divided through replication of DNA which further leads to division of chromosomes & cells. In genes (DNA) there are promoting sequences which promote the

conversion of DNA to mRNA, this process is known as transcription controlled by several enzymes and transcription factors. Transmission of data from language of mRNA to protein held by a process called translation. Translation occurs outside the nucleus whereas the other two held inside the nucleus.

1.7.2.3 Components of Nucleic Acids

Component of nucleic acids varied on the types and structures of those acids. In DNA, backbone of this Deoxy-ribo nucleic acid composed of pentose sugar deoxyribose. Which further bonded with nitrogenous base at alpha 1,9 linkage mainly purine and pyrimidine. In DNA Nucleotides made by nitrogenous bases which are Adenine (A), Guanine (G), Cytosine (C) and Thymine (T). Whereas backbone of RNA is ribose sugar bonded with Adenine (A), Guanine (G), Cytosine (C) and Uracil (U). One purine always bonded with its respective counterpart pyrimidines. Bonds between those is A=T/A=U and C=G.

1.7.2.4 Genome & Proteome

Hans Winkler (1877-1945), a German botanist, coined the word genome in 1920 to characterize "the haploid chromosomal set, which, coupled with the relevant protoplasm, establishes the material foundations of the species..." (Winkler, H.1920. Cristescu, 2019.). A genome is an organism's full genetic information stored in its DNA. The genome contains both genes and non-coding DNA sequences. It covers the complete process of creating, operating, and sustaining an organism as well as passing life on to the next generation. The genome of practically all living organisms on the planet is formed of a molecule called DNA. The genome includes genes that influence the properties of living organisms. The genome comprises chromosomes, and these chromosomes contain genes, which are made up of DNA (Caulfield, T. 2018.). All living creatures are built up of distinct genomes. Individuals, animals, and birds all have unique genomes, and no two humans have the same. The genomic difference between two persons is smaller than the genome difference between a human and a chimp. The hereditary substance in all living cells is the molecule DNA. The genome, like the genes, is formed of DNA. A gene is merely enough DNA to code for one protein, whereas a genome is the complete total of an organism's DNA (byjus.com).

A proteome is the whole set of proteins that an organism expresses. The phrase can also refer to the collection of proteins generated at a certain period in a specific cell or tissue type. The proteome is an expression of the DNA of an organism. In contrast to the genome, which is stable, the proteome varies in response to a variety of circumstances, including the organism's developmental stage and both internal and external environment. Proteomics is the study of the proteome, and it entails studying how proteins operate and interact with one another. Many proteins, for example, fold into complicated three-dimensional structures, and some form complexes with one another to accomplish their activities. Furthermore, proteins undergo changes that

might occur before or after translation. A multitude of approaches can be used to investigate the proteome. Two-dimensional gel electrophoresis, for example, can be used to segregate proteins based on their sizes and charges. The proteome can also be investigated using mass spectrometry, a laboratory method that detects particular proteins inside complicated samples (nature.com).

Figure 18. Detail ultrastructure of DNA & RNA

1.7.3 Importance of the genomic study

Halda river is considered to be the natural breeding ground for Rohu and other major carps and the only river from where fertilized eggs of Rohu are collected. Quality of eggs, fry and fingerling collected from this natural source are far greater than those of induced breeding as induced breeding can lead to genetic degradation. To meet up the protein requirement of our increasing population aquaculture is expanding in our country as a result seed demand is increasing in hatcheries. Poor management of broodstock and lack of scientific approach in those fish farms can lead to gene loss which is a common scenario in Bangladesh (Simonsen, et al., 2005; Rahman, et al., 2009). The gene pools of our indigenous varieties of carps viz: Rohu, Catla & Mrigal have been contaminated (Khatun et al., 2017). On the contrary, the environmental condition of the Halda river is degrading due to anthropogenic activities, as a result, the natural population of major carps is decreasing gradually. So also in natural habitat, this species is at risk. Rohu contributed 10.50% of the total annual fish production of inland water bodies, which is far greater than the other three major carps of Bangladesh (DoF, 2018). But still, we lack sufficient genome label study records for this economically important fish of Halda River in Bangladesh. As we already stated that Halda river is the only river in Bangladesh from where fertilized eggs of major carps are collected so it is very urgent to annotate genetic variability and unique traits of river populations of *L. rohita*. Here we present the first draft genome of pure wild Rohu of river Halda to complement the ongoing increasing aquaculture sector of our country through providing genetic resources, which in turn will allow researchers to carry out further studies of Rohu evolution and resistance to an extreme environment. The genomic information can also be used to avoid loss of genetic diversity, inbreeding depression in the hatchery population and a proper management program can be taken to conserve the pure wild stock of *L. rohita* of river Halda. This information will aid the evolutionary and biological study of Rohu.

Fish species identification mainly lies on their external features of their morphology, including colors, body shape, scale size and count, number and position of fin and their size, number and type of fin rays or measurement of their body parts (Strauss and Bond, 1990). Several internal organs used to determine between extremely close species. Gill rakers, otoliths are also used when none of the former features are available, i.e. to identify fossils or stomach contents (Pierce and Boyle, 1991 ; Granadeiro and Silva, 2000). Previously it was much difficult to identify traits related to adaptation, breeding or disease resistances of organisms only through morphological features. Due to technological advancement it is now easy to solve these questions easily. For this reason, whole genome sequencing (WGS) is an excellent way to unfold the mystery of an organism's features and function through its genomic understanding. To support and strengthen the conservation and finding the uniqueness, this research will present the gene prediction, gene assembly, protein

annotation, comparative genomics and proteomics and annotated protein responsible for muscle growth of *Labeo rohita* from Halda river.

1.7.4 Genome sequencing

The order of DNA nucleotides, or bases, in a genome-the order of As, Cs, Gs, and Ts that make up an organism's DNA-is determined via genome sequencing. In 1944, DNA was labeled as the genetic material by Oswald Theodore Avery. James. D. Watson and Francis Crick in 1953, determined the double helical structure and its four bases i.e. A, T, G and C. As a result of this discovery, the pioneers of the nascent subject of molecular biology were confident that they had discovered the physical foundation of inheritance and essential biological processes. When the process of protein synthesis was discovered, the consensus view was most coherently summarized a half-century ago in 1958 (Crick, 1958) and then again in 1970 (Crick, 1970) by Crick's declaration of "the central dogma of molecular biology" which describes that information basically flows from DNA to RNA to protein, which determines the cellular and organismal phenotype (Shapiro, 2009). With all this knowledge of molecular biology, scientist realised the important of genome sequencing.

1.7.5 Whole Genome Sequencing

Specification of species in genomic DNA and people, making the DNA sequence critical for studying cell structures and functions and deciphering life's secrets. Based on the analysis of genetic variation in individuals and populations, genetics has emerged as an important tool in the conservation of threatened species over the last 40 years. It has also provided insights into diverse areas of conservation biology such as species identification, hybridization, kinship, evolutionary history, effective population size (N_e), population substructure, population connectivity, adaptive genetic variation, local adaptation, and inbreeding (Hedrick and Miller, 1992, Vonder-Heyden et al., 2014, Haig et al., 2016). Human genome project was the first step in the sequencing history though it took several years to complete. At that time sequence technology was still in the process of upgrading. The genome of the pufferfish (*Takifugu rubripes*) was, after the human genome, the second vertebrate genome to be sequenced (Aparicio et al, 2002). DNA sequencing technology and applications have advanced tremendously and serve as the engine of the genome age, which is defined by massive volumes of genomic data and, as a result, a wide range of study fields for scientists worldwide (Lui et al., 2012). The high cost of sequencing technologies made creating high quality sequences difficult for researchers in the first two decades of biological data science. However, because to the genomic data science revolution, it is now possible for researchers to generate high-quality genetic data at a minimal cost. Scientists all across the globe have realized that genetic information on any creature may be extremely valuable, either for the organism or for the benefit

of humanity. Around 3500 complex creatures' genomes have been sequenced till 2018, with just 100 regarded to be reference quality for deep investigation.

1.7.6 Mitochondrial Genome Sequencing

The mitochondrial genome is regarded as the marker of choice for the reconstruction of phylogenetic relationships at several taxonomic levels, from population to phyla, and has been widely used for the resolution of taxonomic controversies (Iwasaki et al., 2013, Gissi et al., 2008). In general, mtDNA is described as a closed circular, double-stranded molecule that is smaller in size (15-17 kb) than the nuclear genome and has some distinguishing features such as relatively stable and compact gene organization, faster replication and maternal inheritance, lack of recombination, and the presence of an orthologous gene. Because of these characteristics, mtDNA is often employed for testing macroevolutionary hypotheses, researching population structure, phylogeography, and phylogenetic connections at multiple taxonomic levels (Saccone et al., 1999, Zhang et al., 2005, Cao et al., 2006). As a result, mtDNA is regarded as a useful tool for researching phylogeny and population genetic studies in vertebrates (Satoh et al., 2016).

1.7.7 Databases of Biological Information

The amount of sequence data has expanded several times since the invention of sequencing technology. Massive technical advances in the computer technology sectors enabled the analysis of terabyte-sized datasets in a blink of an eye. Many databases or digital archives were created by computer professionals to capture, analyze, sort, and share this huge data.

1.7.7.1 DNA sequence databases

National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) of the National Institutes of Health (NIH) has GenBank in Bethesda (Benson et al. 2012) has about 4,50,000 officially described species (Sayers et al. 2022).

The European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL)-Bank Nucleotide Sequence Database (EMBL-Bank), part of the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) at the European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI) in Hinxton, England (Brooksbank et al. 2014, Pakseresht et al. 2014) DNA Database of Japan (DDBJ) at the National Institute of Genetics in Mishima (Ogasawara et al. 2012, Kosuge et al. 2014).

All three databases are coordinated by the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC), and data is shared and exchanged on a daily basis. GenBank, EMBLBank, and DDBJ are databases contained inside NCBI, EBI, and DDBJ, which contain hundreds of other sites for researching sequence data. Scientists can directly donate records to the NCBI, EBI, and DDBJ sequence libraries.

1.7.7.2 Protein Directories

Protein sequences are kept in protein databases. The NCBI holds protein sequence data from GenBank translations as well as data from other external databases such as UniProt (Schneider et al. 2012), The Protein Information Resource (PIR), SWISS-PROT, Protein Research Foundation (PRF), and Protein Data Bank (PDB) (Rose et al. 2012). The EBI, like the NCBI, supplies protein data from the aforementioned sources.

1.7.8 Approaches in Bangladesh

This wave of biological data science took place in Bangladesh in the last decade though it started with decoding of the Jute (*Corchorus olitorius*) genome by a group of Bangladeshi and international scientists in 2010 (Islam et al., 2017). In 2019, Siddiki and colleagues reported the whole genome of Black Bengal Goat (*Capra hircus*), a socioeconomically important goat breed of Bangladesh. Illumina HiSeq2500 sequencing platform was used for library preparation and after assembling, 26,458 gene models were annotated (Siddiki et al., 2019). Bangladesh is endowed with rivers and vast water resources. In a country like Bangladesh where most of the protein source is covered from fishery resources, molecular or genetic level resources of economically valuable fishes are still lacking. As Hilsa (*Tenualosa ilisha*) is the national fish of the country and number one economic fish, considering its importance, a group of scientists unveil the genomic features of this Geographical Indicator (GI) product of Bangladesh (Molla et al., 2019). In 2020, Molla and his colleagues submitted the first draft genome of Hilsa.

For library preparation, they used third generation sequencing platform Illumina HiSeq platform and for assembly preparation SOAPdenovo2 genome assembler and AUGUSTUS was used for gene prediction. The genome size was 710.28 Mb and the N50 value for the scaffolds was 64157 bp. 37,450 protein coding genes were identified of which 29,339 were annotated with other vertebrate genomes. 7,92,939 SNPs were isolated with genome completeness of 78.1%. This research is a milestone in preserving this valuable species and its natural characteristics. It also raises the need for genome level analysis for other economically valuable fishes of the country. Considering the importance of WGS in species conservation and its value in genetic improvements, Integrated Development Foundation (IDF) and Palli Karma-Sahayak Foundation (PKSF) launched a research programme to retrieve the genome sequence of four Indian major carps and Dolphin (*P. gangetica*) of Halda River.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Proteomic signature of muscle fibre hyperplasia

Protein–protein interaction analysis demonstrated the presence of a network containing 56 differentially expressed proteins, and muscle fibre hyperplasia was closely related to a protein– protein network of 12 muscle component proteins. Muscle fibre hyperplasia was also accompanied by decreased abundance in the fatty acid degradation and calcium signalling pathways. In addition, metabolism via the pentose phosphate pathway decreased in grass carp after ingestion of faba bean, leading to haemolysis. These findings could provide a reference for the prevention and treatment of human glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency (“favism”).

Compared with the ordinary grass carp, the hardness and chewiness of crisp grass carp exhibited a 41.97% and 99.57% increase ($p < 0.05$).

Differentially expressed proteins:

Actin Cytoskeleton- catenin alpha-1-like / myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle, partial / talin-2-like Cytoskeleton- catenin alpha-1-like / myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle, partial / talin-2-like Calcium ion binding- Phospholipase C-beta 1

2.2 Computational analysis of transcriptome of Indian major carp

A total of 1671 ESTs of *Labeo rohita* were retrieved from the dbEST database and analysed for functional annotation using various computational approaches. The result indicated 1387 non-redundant (184 contigs and 1203 singletons) putative transcripts with an average length of 542 bp. These 1387 transcript sequences were matched with Refseq_RNA, UniGene and Swiss-Prot on high threshold cut-off for functional annotation along with help of gene ontology and SSRs markers. They developed extensive Perl programming based modules for processing all alignment files, comparing and extracting common hits from all files on a threshold, evaluating statistics for alignment results and assigning gene ontology terms. In this study, 92 putative transcripts predicted as orthologous genes and among those, 44 putative transcripts were annotated with gene ontology terms. The annotated orthologous gene of our result is associated with some very important proteins of *L. rohita* involved in biotic and abiotic stresses and glucose metabolism of spermatogenic cells etc.

Out of 1387 putative transcripts, 256 PTs showed alignment with 664 Refseq_RNA, 258 sequences were aligned with 332 homologous transcripts of *D. rerio* UniGene sets and 145 PTs with 1900 proteins of Swiss-Prot based on significant similarity searches. Among these only 92 (5.8%) transcripts (13 contigs and 79 singletons) were aligned with all the databases and thus fully annotated. While a significant fraction of ESTs data could not be identified by similarity searches, the unidentified

transcripts are valuable resource and can also be taken up for re sequencing, if found important in expression profiling. The unidentified transcripts, if found important in expression profiling can be vital resource after re-sequencing. The predicted genes can further be used for enhancing productivity and controlling disease of *L. rohita*.

2.3 Expressed Sequences and Polymorphisms in Rohu Carp

Expressed genes and polymorphisms were identified in lines of rohu *Labeo rohita* selected for resistance or susceptibility to *Aeromonas hydrophila*, an important bacterial pathogen causing aeromoniasis. All animals were grown in a common environment and RNA from ten individuals from each line pooled for Illumina mRNA-seq. De novo transcriptome assembly produced 137,629 contigs with 40× average coverage. Forty-four percent of the assembled sequences were annotated with gene names and ontology terms. Of these, 3,419 were assigned biological process terms related to “stress response” and 1,939 “immune system”. Twenty-six contigs containing 38 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) were found to map to the *Cyprinus carpio* mitochondrial genome and over 26,000 putative SNPs and 1,700 microsatellite loci were detected. Seventeen percent of the 100 transcripts with coverage data most indicative of higher-fold expression (>5.6 fold) in the resistant line pool showed homology to major histocompatibility (MH), heat shock proteins (HSP) 30, 70 and 90, glycoproteins or serum lectin genes with putative functions affecting immune response. Forty-one percent of these 100 transcripts showed no or low homology to known genes. Of the SNPs identified, 96 showing the highest allele frequency differences between susceptible and resistant line fish.

Trimming of residual adaptor and poor-quality end sequence resulted in 36,352,981 reads with an average read length of 45 bp (Table 2). De novo assembly of the complete dataset resulted in 137,629 contigs with an average contig length of 207 bp (range 100–6,387 bp). Excluding contigs smaller than 200 bp resulted in a total of 40,596 contigs, with an average length of 380 bp. Average coverage across both lanes of data was approximately 40× (around 20× per lane). BLAST searches provided annotation for 47.4% of the contigs; most homology (> 90%) was found to be with genes in the zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) genome. Gene ontology annotation showed that the expressed genes were involved in a diverse range of biological processes (ESM 1). Out of a total of 44,292 contigs with GO-terms, 3,419 (7.7%) were annotated with the biological process “stress response” while 1,939 (4.4%) were annotated with “immune system processes”. Many of the contigs were implicated in broad metabolic, cellular and biological regulation processes (22,191, 30,356 and 16,547 contigs, respectively; ESM 1

2.4 Identification of flesh-quality-attribute-related proteins

In the study, with gel-based proteomics approach, hilsa muscle proteome map was generated and few protein spots, putatively related to flesh quality attributes and selected by comparison with available fish muscle proteome maps (FISHPROT) were

identified by mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF/TOF-MS). Further, the transcript information of the identified proteins was also generated.

1-D and 2-D Gel electrophoresis of hilsa proteins SDS-PAGE profile and a representative proteome of hilsa are presented in Fig 1. 12% SDS polyacrylamide gel resulted in a clear separation of hilsa muscle into distinct protein bands spanning the molecular mass range between 14 to > 205 kDa. Most bands appeared as clear distinct entities, well separated from adjacent protein bands, whereas a few bands appeared stacked with adjacent bands of close molecular weights. The muscle proteome map of hilsa showed the majority of the protein spots were distributed over pI 5.0-8.0 (Fig 2). Selection of putative protein spots by comparison with existing fish muscle proteomes The proteome map of hilsa was compared with that of the other fishes (*Catla catla*, *Rita rita*) available on FISHPROT Database (ref). A total of 17 protein spots were selected based on their Identification of selected proteins by MALDI-TOF/TOF MS

A limited number of gel spots (17 spots) were selected for confirmation of identity by mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF-MS). Out of the 17 spots excised, 12 protein spots representing 11 proteins were identified and these proteins are triosephosphate isomerase; TPI (H1), adenylate kinase (H2), actin alpha skeletal; muscle (H3), phosphatidylethanolamine-binding protein 1 (H9), apolipoprotein A1, APOA1 (H10), guanine nucleotide binding protein (Gq class) (H11), predicted glycogen phosphorylase (H12), DJ-1 protein (H13), lactate dehydrogenase-A; LDHA (H14), cofilin (H15), glyceraldehyde-3 phosphate dehydrogenase partial; G3PDH (H16 and H17) (Table 3). Out of the identified proteins the spots H16 and H17 are proteoforms of G3PDH. Proteoforms are the different forms of proteins produced from the genome with a variety of sequence variations, splice isoforms, and myriad posttranslational modifications and are critical elements in all biological systems. Proteomic analysis needs to provide the identities and abundances of the proteoforms themselves, rather than just their peptide surrogates, although it is a formidable technological challenge (Smith and Kelleher 2018).

2.5 Proteins related to flesh quality of fishes

Majority of the proteins identified in hilsa muscle (GAPDH, TPI, LDH, alpha actin, glycogen phosphorylase (GP), DJ1 and apolipoprotein A1), in the study which was related to flesh quality such as texture, elasticity, firmness, WHC etc. In a previous study, proteins from both myofibrillar (actin, myosin light chain 1 and 2) and sarcoplasmic fractions (GP, creatin kinase and TPI) were found to be closely correlated with firmness (Godiksen et al. 2009) and APOA1 was found to be negatively correlated with raw flesh firmness (Picard et al., 2012). Moreover, ApoA1 play important roles in many functions, like lipid transport and metabolism, via the cholesterol transport pathway. A comparative proteomic study in beef *Longissimus thoracis* revealed that the proteins that are more abundant in less tender flesh are

proteins involved in carbohydrate metabolism like phosphoglucosyltransferase (TPI, GM), LDHB, TPI and GAPDH (Picard, 2012). Similarly, Bernard et al. (2007) showed DJ1 (Hsp40) to be an effective indicator of tenderness. This has protein DJ1 has anti apoptotic role and can slow down the process of cell death during the early stages of transformation of muscle to meat and also have been shown to maintain cellular metabolic homeostasis via modulating ROS levels in murine skeletal muscles further revealing a role of DJ-1 in maintaining efficient fuel. As a result, higher levels of this protein are associated with tender meat. In fish muscle, actin is attached to thin filament proteins (troponins and tropomyosins) and proteins constitutive to cytoskeletal structure (dystrophin, filamin or α -actinin) Therefore, maintaining actin in complexes and minimising release of intact actin is related with a firm texture. Similarly, TPI along with other glycolytic enzymes (fructose bisphosphate, aldolase and GAPDH) is attached to the thin myofilaments and degradation of such actin-glycolytic enzymes complexes may have an impact on thin filament proteolysis and texture.

2.6 Muscle proteomics of Indian major carp *Catla catla*

Skeletal muscle proteomics aims at global identification, cataloging and biochemical characterization of the entire protein complement of voluntary contractile tissues. A reference muscle proteome map for *Catla catla* was generated by using 2-D gel electrophoresis and 70 protein spots representing 22 proteins have been identified by MALDI-TOF MS. Out of the 70 protein spots identified, 43 were identified as metabolic enzymes involved in carbohydrate (32), protein (1), lipid (5) and nucleotide (5) metabolism. Another 19 spots were found to be cytoskeletal proteins, of which 14 are creatine kinase (CK). Three proteins were identified to be associated with signal transduction and five were categorized separately based on their functions

2.6.1 Partial gene sequences of gene coding:

Pyruvate kinase, creatine Kinase, beta actin, phosphorylase kinase, adenylate kinase, enolase, phosphohistidine phosphatase, PDZ and LIM, CapZB, aspartate aminotransferase, glyceraldehyde 3 phosphate dehydrogenase, apolipoprotein, fructose 1,6 bisphosphate, lactate dehydrogenase, phosphoglycerate kinase, transferrin* 16 hsp47, hsp70, hsc71, Hsp60, Hsp90, 18s RNA

2.7 Chromosome level assembly

Xie et al. (2022) did a chromosomal level assembly of *Cephalopholis sonnerati* (Tomato Hind) from PacBio sequencing and Hi-C technologies and discovered a genome of 1043.66 Mb with a contig N50 length of 2.49 Mb. A total of 795 contigs orientated into 24 chromosomes with 97.2% complete BUSCOs were discovered. From a total of 21,130 predicted genes, 94.26% were functionally annotated. Mecat2 (Xiao et al. 2017) was used for the draft genome assembly, and gcpp 1.9.0 was used to polish the original assembly and repair the mistakes of the primary assembly.

BUSCO v3.0 (Simo et al., 2015) with *actinoperygii odb9* was utilized to assess genome wholeness. Hi-C sequencing libraries were mapped to the polished genome utilizing bwa 0.7.17 (Li, 2013) to generate Hi-C affiliated scaffolds for the assembly of pseudochromosomes. Contigs were aggregated and orientated using Lachesis (Burton et al., 2013), and the assembly's visual debugging was performed using Juicer v1.6.2 (Durand et al., 2016). Two approaches, such as de novo and homology-based techniques, were used to identify the repetitive sequences.

RepeatMasker 4.0.9 (Chen 2004) was used for homology-based repeat content marketing strategy, however RepeatModeler (Flynn et al., 2020) was used for de novo repeat content identification, which was a mixture of two programs, namely RECON v1.08 (Bao and Eddy 2002) and RepeatScout v1.0.5 (Price et al., 2005). The LTR FINDER v1.0.7 (Xu and Wang, 2007) and Tandem Repeat Finder (TRF) packages were used to recognize long terminal repeats and tandem repetitions (Benson 1999).

2.8 First phase of Genome Sequencing

The order of nucleic acid residues in biological samples needs to be determined for a variety of scientific applications. Different researchers have attempted to create tools and techniques over the past 50 years that will make this effort simpler, like sequencing both RNA and DNA molecules. The field of data science has advanced significantly over this period. The ability to sequence tiny oligonucleotide primers down to a single gene and then a whole genome set has really been made possible by technical developments. To obtain a functionally meaningful result from DNA sequencing, a variety of stages and procedures are required, involving the extraction of DNA, disintegration, base analysis, and ultimately assessment of the sequence data. Sequence analysis is crucial in so many fields of contemporary biology. Analysis of two different organisms' homologous genes, evolutionary history, and signaling pathways can be done using genome sequencing. Sequence information that aids in perceiving illness states caused by genetic divergence should have a significant impact on biological research and medical practice. But none of these advancements happened overnight. It took specialist researchers decades to sift through this hodgepodge of letters (ATGC...TACG) and unearth the underlying significance encoded in an organism's genome or genetic codes.

The three-dimensional structure of DNA was famously discovered by Watson and Crick in 1953 using crystallographic data from Rosalind Franklin and Maurice Wilkins (Watson et al., 1953; Zallen et al., 2003). Their efforts contributed to the conceptual development of DNA replication and protein coding based on nucleic acids. But it took some time before researchers could read or sequence DNA. DNA molecules were more difficult to distinguish from one another because they were longer and contained fewer, more similar units (Hutchison, 2007). The methods used to determine the protein chain sequence did not seem to translate well to studies of nucleic acids. Coming up with fresh approaches was necessary. A small number of

relatively pure RNA species, such as microbial ribosomal or transfer RNA, or the genome of single-stranded RNA bacteriophages, whose DNA molecules are incredibly short compared to those of eukaryotic cells, were the initial focus of research. Up until recently, analytical chemistry was the only method available to scientists to determine the order of nucleotides. Using the alanine tRNA from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, Robert Holley and associates created the first comprehensive nucleic acid sequence in 1965 (Holley et al., 1965). Four years after the discovery of the first protein-coding gene sequence (Jou et al., 1972), the complete genome sequences were developed (Fiers et al., 1976).

Bacteriophage 6X174 was the first DNA genome that Sanger and colleagues were able to sequence (Sanger et al., 1977). Sanger sequencing underwent a number of developments and improvements after that, which helped to pave the way for the creation of modern DNA sequencing equipment. The human genome was finished in 2001, and since then, genomic data science has advanced significantly. Public databases like NCBI Genbank, EMBL, and DDBJ, among others, now contain many complete or incomplete genomes and genes of eukaryotic and prokaryotic species. The interest in genomic data science, which has multiplied, is causing those databases to update quickly.

2.9 Genetic Approaches on Cultured Rohu

The importance of Rohu in aquaculture is beyond imagination. This fastest-growing species is in high demand in South Asian aquaculture. Much research has been conducted on Rohu to understand its feeding habits and breeding biology, which is now well understood. Molecular level studies, especially for farmed Rohu, have been carried out by several scientists, though the number is pretty insignificant. Though molecular level research on this economically important species is still somewhat lacking, the use of genetic and advanced molecular tools are already in practice in the case of farmed Rohu, giving scientists a keen insight into the biological features of Rohu. To understand the mechanisms of genes or transcripts associated with growth, metabolism, immunity, stress response and reproduction, several attempts have been taken by scientists in cloning and emphasize different genes associated with those traits. In the NCBI database, mRNA sequences (5130), Expressed Sequence Tag (4798), cDNAs (332) of Rohu have been submitted in recent years. All of these transcripts accounted for immunity, reproduction, metabolism and growth related traits. **(Table 8.)**

2.9.1 Gene Cloning and Expression Profiling

Gene expression profiling helps in understanding the function of genes. This tactic is now being utilised by researchers in farmed Rohu. Pradhan and colleagues investigated the role of Follicle-stimulating hormone (Fsh) and luteinizing hormone (LA) during seasonal gonadal development in *L. rohita*. Full-length cDNAs of shra and thegrba from Rohu testis using RACE (Rapid amplification of cDNA ends) were

cloned and analysed their expression along with fsh and th by quantitative real time PCR (qRT-PCR) assay at various gonadal developmental stages of the annual reproductive cycle. Full-length Rohu fshra and thcgrba cDNA encodes 670 and 716 amino acids respectively, and in adult fish, they were widely expressed in brain, pituitary, gonad, liver, kidney, head kidney, heart, muscle, gill, fin, eye and intestine. In male, both fish and fshra transcripts showed high levels of expression during spermatogenesis, however, in females, expression level was found to be higher in the fully grown oocyte stages. The expression of Rohu lh and lhcgrba mRNA increased with increment of gonadosomatic index and showed highest level during spermiation stage in male and fully matured oocyte stage in female. These results together may suggest the involvement of fshra and thegrba in regulating function of seasonal gonadal development in Rohu (Pradhan et al., 2018).

Expression profiling of Sox2 (Sry-related box-2) in farmed Rohu has been done by Patra and colleagues in 2015. This study aimed to clone and characterize the Sax2 complementary DNA from the testes of Rohu. The resulting cDNA sequence contains an open reading frame 936 nucleotides with typical features. They provided evidence that Sox2 is abundantly expressed in Rohu proliferating SSCs (Spermatogonial stem cell) and connected with stem cell maintenance (Patra et al., 2015). Patra and colleagues in 2018 for the first time reported the relation of Rohu Nanog (LrNanog) gene in the embryonic development and maintenance of spermatogonial stem cells of farmed carp, *L. rohita*. The cDNA contains an open reading frame of 1,161 nucleotides and analyses of genomic structure revealed similarity with its mammalian counterparts. They have done tissue distribution analysis and found the existence of LrNanog transcripts only in the adult gonads suggesting its relation with the maternal inheritance and male germ cell development (Patra et al., 2018). Pousfl is a transcriptional regulator related to maintenance of embryonic and spermatogonial stem cells in mammals. Teleost Pou2 is an ortholog of mammalian Pou5f1. Mohapatra and colleagues reported that, in farmed *L. rohila* Pou2 was abundantly expressed proliferating Rohu spermatogonial cells and hence participates in stem cell maintenance (Mohapatra et al., 2014). Patnaik and colleagues cloned and characterised the cDNA sequence of Activin receptor type IIA (ActRIIA) in *L. rohita* ActRIIA is an important regulator of reproduction and growth both in vertebrates and teleosts. In this 1,587 bp of Rohu AaRIIA cDNA was found to be encoded for 528 amino acids. Expression profiling revealed its relation in promoting oocyte maturation, skeletal muscle development and spermatogenesis in Rohu (Patnaik et al., 2017). Another important regulator of reproduction in mammalian and presumably non the mammalian species is kisspeptin. Saha and colleagues reported the function of kisspeptin (kissi and kiss2) genes at various gonadal developmental stages of the annual reproductive cycle of *L. rohita*. Full-length cDNA of kiss1 and kiss2 was cloned and characterised by RACE (rapid amplification of cDNA ends) and quantitative real time PCR (qRT-PCR) was used in analysing their expressions

in the modulation of brain-pituitary-gonad (BPG) axis during different gonadal maturity stages of *L. rohita* (Saha et al., 2016). Besides this, Mohapatra and colleagues conducted a study on the function of Promyocytic leukaemia zinc finger (Plzf) genes on the proliferation of spermatogonial stem cells of a farmed Rohu (Mohapatra and Barman, 2014).

In aquaculture practices, fish farms often face the crisis of bacterial, fungal and parasitic outbreaks causing massive death of fishes. In the case of Rohu culture, disease break is a usual thing. Researchers conducted molecular level study on the immune responses of these farmed Rohu. Several immune related genes or transcripts of farmed Rohu have been cloned and emphasizes by challenge tests. The Toll-like receptors (TLRs) are an important class of innate immune receptors responsible for detecting pathogens and activating non-specific and quick immune responses in the host. Different workers tried to clone and characterise these TLRs in farmed Rohu to investigate their mechanisms in immune responses.

The role of Toll-like receptors (TLRS) TLR4 in innate immunity of *L. rohita* was investigated by Samanta and colleagues. Full-length cDNA of *L. rohita* TLR4 (LrTLR4) was cloned and consisted of 2,729 bp with a single ORF of 2,469 bp encoding a polypeptide of 822 amino acids (Aa) with a predicted molecular mass of 94.753 kDa. Structurally, LrTLR+ consisted of 25LRRs (leucine rich repeat regions), one TM (trans-membrane) domain and one TIR (Toll/ interleukin-1 receptor) domain, and was similar to higher vertebrate's TLR4. Phylogenetically, LrTLR4 exhibited the highest (85%) identity with the common carp TLR4b amino acids sequence, and formed a separate subgroup in the phylogenetic tree. LrTLR4 was widely expressed in all tested organs and tissues, and tissues highest expression was detected in blood and the lowest in the eye. In response to LPS-stimulation, LrTLR4 was induced with the activation of MyD88- dependent and TRIF-dependent 22mphasize pathway resulting in pro-inflammatory cytokines (interleukin 6 and 8) and type I IFN gene expression. Infection of Rohu with a Gram-negative fish pathogen (*Aeromonas hydrophila*), also Together, these findings suggest the important role of 7LR4 in LPS activates Lri sensing and augmentation of innate immunity against Gram-negative bacterial infection in fish (Samanta et al., 2017).

Teleosts have a highly sophisticated and tightly controlled adaptive immune system. Immunoglobulins make up the most important humoral component of the adaptive immune system. One of the most important immunoglobulin is IgM involved in the systemic and mucosal immunity of a host against disease-causing organisms (Salinas et al., 2011). Saravanan and colleagues studied the expression profile of IgM in the heavy chain of Rohu. They discovered that Rohu's IgM heavy chain cDNA was 1994 bp long and encoded a polypeptide of 576 amino acid residues. Their research claims Cysteine, tryptophan, and amino acid motifs like 'YYCAR' and 'FDYWGKGT-VTV-S' are all found in the sequence. The Rohu IgM heavy chain's domains were confirmed by the projected 3D model. The Rohu's IgM heavy chain gene clustered

with that of other cyprinid fishes, according to phylogenetic tree analysis. The kidney, spleen, and colon had the highest levels of IgM heavy chain gene expression, according to tissue distribution study. The expression of the IgM heavy chain gene in the Rohu kidney was found to be up-regulated, peaking 7 days after the *Aeromonas hydrophila* challenge. Furthermore, the IgM heavy chain gene was shown to be strongly expressed in significant lymphoid tissues, and bacterial stimulation had an impact on its expression, confirming its involvement in the adaptive humoral immune response (Saravanan et al., 2020).

Table 08. : List of genes/transcripts cloned and characterized in Rohu with their biological functions (Rasal and Sundaray, 2020)

Gene Name	Gene symbol	Accession ID	Full length/Partial	Biological role	Reference
1. <i>Growth Hormone</i>	GH	AF418921.1	Full 1180 bp	Growth	Thayanithy et al. (2002)
2. <i>Complement component 3</i>	C3	AM773825.1	Partial	Immunity	Mishra et al. (2009)
3. <i>Ceruloplasmin</i>	Cln	JX010736.1	Full 3355 bp	Immunity	Sahoo et al. (2013)
4. <i>Toll-like receptor 2</i>	TLR2	HQ293022.1	Full 2691 bp	Immunity	Samanta et al. (2012)
5. <i>Nucleotide binding and oligomerization domain-1 receptor</i>	NOD1	JN794079.1	Full 3168 bp	Immunity	Swain et al. (2012)
6. <i>Doublesex and mab-3 related transcription factor</i>	Dmrt	Not submitted	Full 907 bp	Reproduction	Sahoo et al. (2019)
7. <i>Laboratory of genetics and physiology 2</i>	Lgp2	MN029108.1	Full 2034 bp	Immunity and RLR-signalling pathway	Mohanty et al. (2020)
8. <i>Immunoglobulin M</i>	IgM	KX268324.1	Full 1994 bp	Immunity	Saravanan et al. (2019)
9. <i>Myxovirus resistance</i>	Mx	KR349112.1	Full 2297 bp	Immunity	Das et al. (2019)
10. <i>Apolipoprotein A-I</i>	ApoA1	KC934748.1	Full 771 bp	Immunity	Mohapatra et al. (2016)

11.	<i>Interleukin-1 receptor-associated kinase</i>	IRAK1	MK967704.1	Full 2765 bp	Immunity	Sadangi et al. (2020)
12.	<i>Sex determining region Y box 2</i>	Sox2	KJ499194.1	Full 936 bp	Reproduction	Patra et al. (2015)
13.	<i>Follicle-stimulating hormone and luteinizing hormone</i>	Fsh and Lh	JX678220.1 JX678284.1	Full 3633 bp 2976 bp	Reproduction	Pradhan et al. (2018)
14.	<i>Toll-like receptor 22</i>	TLR22	KJ187307.1	Full 2,838 bp	Immunity	Samanta et al. (2014)
15.	<i>Activin Receptor Type IIA</i>	Act R- IIA	KU870464.1	Full 1672 bp	Reproduction	Patnaik et al. (2017)
16.	<i>Interleukin 15</i>	Il-15	KJ486472.1	Full 1064 bp	Immunity	Das et al. (2015)
17.	<i>Myosin light polypeptide chain 2</i>	Mylz2	GQ487579.1	Full 448 bp	Growth	Mohanta et al. (2014)
18.	<i>Nanog (homeobox transcription factor)</i>	Nanog	KX268304.1	Full 1,161 bp	Spermatogonial stem cells	Patra et al. (2018)
19.	<i>Kisspeptin1 and Kisspeptin 2</i>	Kiss1 ,Kiss2	KF737179.1 KF695115.1	Full 660 bp, 649 bp	Reproduction	Saha et al. (2016)
20.	<i>POU domain, class 2</i>	Pou5f1	GU443948.1	Full 1419 bp	Reproduction	Mohapatra et al. (2014)
21.	<i>Connective tissue growth factor</i>	CTGF	KY940466.1	Full 2421 bp	Stress	Rashid et al. (2019)

22.	<i>Type-I interferon</i>	I-IFN	HQ667143.1	Full 665 bp	Immunity	Parhi et al. (2014)
23.	<i>Toll-like receptor 4</i>	TLR4	KX218428.1	Full 2729 bp	Immunity	Samanta et al. (2017)
24.	<i>Toll-like receptor 3</i>	TLR3	JN886779.1	Partial 2619 bp	Immunity	Samanta et al. (2013)
25.	<i>Interferon gamma</i>	IFN-c	KJ874352.1	Full 927 bp	Immunity	Swain et al. (2015)
26.	<i>Interleukin-10</i>	Il-10	HM245962.1	Full 1467 bp	Immunity	Karan et al. (2014)
27.	<i>Ghrelin</i>	Ghrl	LC271259.1	Full 453 bp	Metabolism	Dar et al. (2020)
28.	<i>Galectin 9</i>	Gl-9	Not submitted	Full 1534 bp	Immunity	Mushtaq et al. (2018)
29.	<i>Promyelocytic leukaemia zinc finger</i>	Plzf	GU338377.1	Full 2298 bp	Reproduction	Mohapatra and Barman 2014
27.	<i>Hypoxia inducible oxygenase 1</i>	Hmox1	Not submitted	Full 3715 bp	Stress	Rashid et al. (2020)

2.9.2 Marker Discovery with Whole-genome Sequencing

Due to genome and transcriptome sequencing, the SNP database is growing rapidly. Geneticists can pick fish with superior genetic material for future generations based on SNPs linked to performance and production traits. On the other hand DNA markers are utilized in population genetic studies for a variety of reasons, including species identification, evolutionary depiction, and as indicators of production or performance qualities (Rasal et al., 2017). Mitochondrial (mt) genes have also been used as genetic variation markers for species identification and evolution. Hamilton and colleague studied on the SNPs and silicoDArT markers of a breeding population of Rohu from Halda, Jamuna, and Padma rivers. They have discovered 9,157 SNPs and 14,411 silicoDArT markers using diversity arrays technology (DArT) and

genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS) platform to sequence the fin clips of Rohu collected from these rivers. After quality checking, 1,985 polymorphic indels (SNPs) were utilized to examine the population structures between different river systems. Based on low pairwise F_{ST} estimates among the rivers (<0.005) and SNP genotyping, the Rohu populations showed little genetic divergence, probably due to the founding groups close relatedness (Hamilton et al., 2019).

Sahu and colleagues conducted a study on the identification of reproduction-related genes and SSR-markers through expressed sequence tags analysis in Rohu. They found 236 SSR markers in the brain-pituitary-gonad-liver (BPGL) axis of *L. rohita* collected during the post-preparatory phase from 3631 distinct sequences related with reproduction where AG was the most repeated motif accounting for 28.16%. They also observed 182 unique sequences linked to reproduction-related genes, primarily under the GO terms reproduction, neuropeptide hormone activity, hormone and receptor binding, receptor activity, signal transduction, embryonic development, cell to cell signalling, cell death, and anti-apoptosis process. Several important reproduction-related genes, such as zona pellucida sperm-binding protein 3, aquaporin-12, spermine oxidase, sperm associated antigen 7, testis expressed 261, progesterone receptor membrane component, Neuropeptide Y, and Pro-opiomelanocortin, were reported for the first time in their study (Sahu et al., 2013).

Das and colleagues submitted the first draft genome of a farmed Rohu of the Jayanti breed in 2020, which was the most significant contribution in the case of cultured Rohu. For sequencing reasons, a male Rohu from the seventh generation of a selective breeding experiment run by ICAR-CIIA was chosen. A multi-array sequencing strategy such as Roche 454 (GS FLX), Illumina (Miseq and Nextseq 500), Ion Torrent (PGM), and PacBio (Sequel) was selected for sequencing purposes. For assembling several assemblers were used such as MaSuRCA, SOAPdenovo2, Celera and CANU assembler. The assembled genome was 1.48 Gb, which is more than 98% of the estimated genome size that is 1.5 Gb. The assembly is done upto scaffold level and the BUSCO analysis showed 95.6% completeness. The assembly yielded 259,627 contigs and 13,623 scaffolds, with N50 values of 30.6 kb and 1.95Mb for contigs and scaffolds, respectively. There are 26400 protein-coding genes in the genome, and tRNAScan predicts 2516 tRNAs. All 3,193 SNP markers had sequence information that matched at unique places in 667 scaffolds, encompassing around 80% of the genome. The 667 scaffolds, totaling 1.18 Gb, were distributed across 1,416 cM of the genome, which corresponded to the Rohu linkage groups. 146 SSR loci encompassing 25 Rohu linkage groups were also matched. Phylogenetic analysis comparing farmed Rohu with other otophysan species revealed that Rohu belongs to the Otophysi clade (Das et al., 2020).

Chapter 3

Materials and Methods

3.1 Data collection:

In 2020, the Halda River Research Laboratory of the University of Chittagong collected a sample of *Labeo rohita* from the Halda River in Hathazari, Chattogram. I have used our previously sequenced raw data submitted on the NCBI which can be found in the Data Description section in detail. In the previous year, Halda River Research Laboratory assembled a scaffold level genome with that raw data. My goal is to reassemble the genome to chromosome level for better understanding the genetic variation of *Labeo rohita* from Halda river.

After obtaining the raw data from NCBI, I proceeded to clean and trim the dataset in order to remove adapters and other sequencing errors, as well as to go through various preprocessing steps prior to genome assembly, employing BFC (Pevzner et al., 2001) and Trimmomatic (Bolger et al., 2014). BWA-MEM algorithm from Burrows-Wheeler Aligner (BWA) and Samtools used to map the raw data with *Gallus gallus* reference genome to check the mapping quality and overall homogeneity.

3.2 Genome assembly

In order to get the best results from one of them, several genome assemblers were used. Genome assembly with Illumina raw data was performed using ABySS, SOAPdenovo2, MaSuRCA (Aleksey et al. 2013), and Platanus. With the aid of the reference genome, the assembled genome was polished using SSPACE, Pilon, MUMmer, minimap2, and a custom polishing script written in Python and Shell script. To polish the assembled genome and build the chromosome level assembly in this study, reference genomes from *Danio rerio* (Zebrafish), *Cyprinus carpio* (Common Carp), *Catla catla* (CIFA Catla, India), and *Labeo rohita* (Rohu) were used. Finally, reference genome with MUMmer, minimap, JCVI ALLMAPS used to align, mapping, order and orient the chromosomes to create a superior chromosome level assembly which is vital for further research on GWAS, specific traits or attributes, and proteomic analysis.

3.3 Assembly quality assurance and benchmarking

Using QCAST (Gurevich et al. 2013) and BUSCO (Manni et al. 2021) tools, I compared the assembled genome's quality to the reference genome. I was able to compare the assembled genome to the reference genome using QCAST, and the BUSCO benchmark provided the gene completeness score.

3.4 Functional genome analysis

Functional genome analysis indicates the analysis of genes in the genome those function accordingly. By functional genome analysis we can figure out the actual functions of the numerous number of genes, their pathways, association and inter-

relationship with other proteins, extract the exact protein that we want to analyse for our further studies. In my study, I analyzed the raw data to genome assembly, gene prediction or gene annotation, protein prediction and annotation for searching muscle proteins and also analyzed the KEGG pathway to find out protein-protein interrelationships.

3.4.1 Repeat elements and divergent determination:

To determine the repeat elements and divergence of the genome, RepeatMasker (Tarailo-Graovac et al 2009), RepeatModeler (Flynn et al 2020), RepeatScout (Price et al 2005), and RepBase (Bao et al 2015) were used.

3.4.2 Gene prediction

The AUGUSTUS and MAKER pipelines were used to perform ab-initio gene prediction on all complete and partial genes for further processing and use.

3.4.3 Protein prediction and annotation

To annotate the proteins, identify domains and protein function, and match gene ontology with public databases, InterProScan (Quevillon et al 2005) and Pannzer2 (Törönen et al 2018) were used.

3.4.4 Quantitative trait loci analysis

Using quantitative trait analysis by NCBI, Uniprot database, important traits related to muscle development and muscle growth will be identified and assessed. Several custom machine learning trained algorithms and pre-existing bioinformatics tools (for example, BLASTx, Blast2Go, BLASTp, tBLASTn) were used. Comparative trait analysis performed on native and commercial species. In this thesis I preferred muscle development and muscle growth traits for comparative trait analysis.

3.4.5 GWAS and Pathway analysis of economically important traits

The NCBI, KEGG, Public gene ontology database, and computational biology approach will be used to analyze any gene involved in economically important traits, from biochemical reaction to cellular and molecular function, influencing the physiological pathway, metabolism, and expression of phenotypes.

3.4.6 Data visualization

To visualize final datasets, custom R packages and MS Excel used in conjunction with cloud computing web servers.

Figure 19. Pipeline of this comparative genome and proteome analysis with pathway.

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 Chromosome level assembled genome:

A chromosome level genome was constructed with 25 pair chromosomes, 1 mitochondrial circular dna and 2376 unplaced scaffolds. The total size of the genome was 1159574983 base pairs, N50 of 35.5 Mbp, and maximum sized scaffold with 44.86 Mbp, providing a high quality assembled genome with very few short fragments on the genome. GC content was 36.74 percent. Details can be found in the data description section.

Table 09. Genome statistics

Name	Our study	Reference genome	Indian Jayanti	CIFA	RefSeq BAU
Total ungapped length	1101 Mbp	945 Mbp	1427 Mbp		945.5 Mbp
Number of sequences	2401¹	2870	13523		2869
Number of bases	1,159,574,983	1,126,558,565	1,484,730,970		992,683,291
N50	35.5 Mbp²	32.5 Mbp	1.9 Mbp		37.9 Mbp²
L50	9³	13	182		12
Min base	16779	1479	500		-
Max base	44.86 Mbp	45.29 Mbp	15 Mbp		-
Unplaced	2376	2844	13523		2844

^{1.} Smaller number in sequences is better as a less fragmented genome.

^{2.} Bigger number in N50 is better. Showing overall large sized scaffolds.

^{3.} Smaller L50 is better. Showing overall large sized scaffolds.

Figure 20. Comparison of total ungapped length among various studies.

Figure 21. Comparison of number of sequences among various studies.

Figure 22. Comparison of N50 among various studies.

Figure 23. Comparison of L50 among various studies.

4.2 Gene completeness benchmark

BUSCO gene completeness benchmark used to perform a gene completeness check with reference characteristics of Super kingdom: Eukaryotes and Class: Actinopterygii. Output from the BUSCO benchmark showed in **Table 10.** below.

Table 10. BUSCO gene completeness benchmark

	Eukaryota	Actinopterygii
Completeness in %	C:95.7%[S:93.3%,D:2.4%],F:4.3%,M:0.0%	C:93.5%[S:92.3%,D:1.2%],F:3.2%,M:3.3%
Complete BUSCOs (C)	244	3400
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs (S)	238	3358
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs (D)	6	42
Fragmented BUSCOs (F)	11	115
Missing BUSCOs (M)	0	125
Total BUSCO groups searched	255	3640

Figure 24. Gene completeness with Class: Actinopterygii (Klein, 1885)

Figure 25. Gene completeness with Superkingdom: Eukaryota (Whittaker & Margulis, 1978)

4.3 Repeat elements on the genome

A total of 13% percent of repeats was found on the genome. On all the repeated content there were 2.95% retroelements, 2.01% LTR elements, 6.51% DNA transposons, 0.11% satellites, 2.90% simple repeats were predicted.

4.4 Functional gene prediction and protein annotation

A total of 47568 numbers of genes was predicted with AUGUSTUS. A protein coding region was found where a total of more than 16000 gene ontology was detected with their respective pathway. Protein annotation with gene ontology and pathway mapping was done by eggNOG-Mapper and Panzzer2 tools with the dependency on BLASTx, BLASTn, tBLASTn, KEGG database, NCBI Gene Ontology, Entrez Direct, Ensembl and EBI ENA database.

Table 11. Number of genes per chromosome in my study

Chr.	Genes	Annotated	Gene Ontology	KEGG Pathway	Non-coding, Pseudogenes
1	1273	1053	746	714	220
2	1407	1146	790	801	261
3	1464	1209	803	791	255
4	1163	862	533	558	301
5	1662	1323	984	970	339
6	1190	995	758	724	195
7	1630	1260	870	853	370
8	1267	1049	785	733	218
9	1279	1004	706	664	275
10	1119	910	656	631	209
11	907	748	584	539	159
12	1001	830	639	596	171
13	1223	971	715	667	252
14	1049	838	602	581	211
15	1161	865	586	595	296
16	1502	1106	739	727	396
17	1239	981	729	668	258
18	1155	861	563	553	294
19	1193	940	666	633	253
20	1130	963	748	694	167
21	1106	876	672	638	230
22	1065	789	471	500	276
23	1035	865	607	605	170
24	927	716	516	486	211
25	1006	830	622	598	176

Table 12. Showing summary of table for genomic data per chromosome

Summary Table					
	Genes	Annotated	Gene Ontology	KEGG Pathway	Non-coding, Pseudogenes
Total Chr.	30153	23990	17115	16461	6163
Unplaced	17415	9352	2633	4285	8063
Total	47568	33342	19723	20741	14226

Figure 26. Showing chromosome wise gene distribution (My study)

Figure 27. Annotated gene proteins and non-coding pseudogenes per chromosome.

Figure 28. Showing chromosome wise comparison between annotated proteins, non-coding & pseudogenes distribution among total genes.

Figure 29. Annotated gene proteins and non-coding pseudogenes per chromosome among total genes

Figure 30. Visualization of Summary table for total genes, annotated proteins and non coding & pseudogenes.

Figure 31. Extended Pie Diagram of placed & unplaced total genes, annotated proteins and non coding; pseudogenes

Figure 32. Visualization of genes, annotated proteins, gene ontology, KEGG pathway, Non-coding/Pseudogenes per chromosome

Table 13. RefSeq BAU Genome Statistics

Chr	Genes	Annotated	Non-coding, Pseudogenes
1	1259	1094	165
2	1313	1156	157
3	1475	1242	233
4	915	747	168
5	1439	1306	133
6	1130	1026	104
7	1426	1228	198
8	1152	1032	120
9	983	873	110
10	1013	891	122
11	878	751	127
12	919	823	96
13	977	893	84
14	880	779	101
15	987	864	123
16	1267	1124	143
17	1006	886	120
18	864	764	100
19	1063	916	147
20	1055	924	131
21	1089	941	148
22	1025	813	212
23	964	868	96
24	722	660	62
25	906	777	129
Total Chr	26707	23378	3329
Unplaced	5024	3248	1776
Total	31731	26626	5105

Figure 33. Showing chromosome wise gene distribution (refseq)

Figure 34. Showing chromosome wise comparison between annotated proteins, non-coding & pseudogenes distribution among total genes (refseq)

Figure 35. Annotated proteins & non-coding, pseudogenes per chromosome (Refseq)

Figure 36. Visualization of Summary table for total genes, annotated proteins and non coding & pseudogenes (refseq)

Chapter: 5

Comparative Analysis & Discussion

5.1 Comparative analysis of genome

Comparative analysis made with my chromosome level assembled data of *Labeo rohita* from Halda River, Chattogram with chromosome level assembled data of *Labeo rohita*, strain BAU-BD-2019 from riverine area of Rangpur district.

NCBI Accession ID. of Reference Sequence: GCF_022985175.1

NCBI Accession ID. of My Study: Not uploaded yet

Below Table showing chromosome wise gene number variation between my study and refseq.

Table 14. Chromosome wise gene distribution between my study and refseq.

Chr.	Genes My study	Genes Refseq BAU-BD-2019
1	1273	1259
2	1407	1313
3	1464	1475
4	1163	915
5	1662	1439
6	1190	1130
7	1630	1426
8	1267	1152
9	1279	983
10	1119	1013
11	907	878
12	1001	919
13	1223	977
14	1049	880
15	1161	987
16	1502	1267
17	1239	1006
18	1155	864
19	1193	1063
20	1130	1055
21	1106	1089
22	1065	1025
23	1035	964
24	927	722
25	1006	906
Total Chr.	30153	26707
Unplaced	17415	5024
Total	47568	31731

Figure 37. Comparison of genes per chromosome between my study & refseq.

Figure 38. Comparison of genes per chromosome between my study & refseq with total no. of genes

Figure 39. Visualisation of Comparison between my study and refseq of total placed and unplaced genes along with total genes.

Table 15. Chromosome wise non-coding and pseudogenes distribution between my study and refseq.

Chr.	Non-coding, Pseudogenes My study	Non-coding, Pseudogenes Refseq
1	220	165
2	261	157
3	255	233
4	301	168
5	339	133
6	195	104
7	370	198
8	218	120
9	275	110
10	209	122
11	159	127
12	171	96
13	252	84
14	211	101
15	296	123
16	396	143
17	258	120
18	294	100
19	253	147
20	167	131
21	230	148
22	276	212
23	170	96
24	211	62
25	176	129
Total Chr.	6163	3329
Unplaced	8063	1776
Total	14226	5105

Figure 40. Visualising comparison of non-coding and pseudogenes distribution between my study and refseq per chromosome

Figure 41. Visualisation of Comparison between my study and refseq of total placed and unplaced non-coding,pseudogenes along with summation

5.2 Comparative analysis of proteome

Comparative analysis made with my chromosome level assembled data of *Labeo rohita* from halda river, Chattogram with chromosome level assembled data of *Labeo rohita*, strain BAU-BD-2019 from riverine area of Rangpur district.

NCBI Accession ID. of Reference Sequence: GCF_022985175.1

Below Table 5.2.1. showing chromosome wise protein number variation between my study and refseq.

Table 16. Chromosome wise annotated gene protein distribution between my study and refseq.

Chr.	Annotated Proteins My study	Annotated Proteins Refseq BAU-BD-2019
1	1053	1094
2	1146	1156
3	1209	1242
4	862	747
5	1323	1306
6	995	1026
7	1260	1228
8	1049	1032
9	1004	873
10	910	891
11	748	751
12	830	823
13	971	893
14	838	779
15	865	864
16	1106	1124
17	981	886
18	861	764
19	940	916
20	963	924
21	876	941
22	789	813
23	865	868
24	716	660
25	830	777
Total Chr.	23990	23378
Unplaced	9352	3248
Total	33342	26626

Figure 42. Comparison of proteins per chromosome between my study & refseq.

Figure 43. Comparison of proteins per chromosome between my study & refseq with total no. of annotated genes/proteins

Figure 44. Visualising comparison of total annotated gene proteins distribution between my study and refseq.

5.3 Orthologs

Orthologs are genes found in various species that can be traced back to the same gene in their common ancestor's genome (Fitch 1970). Fitch separated them from paralogs (genes arising from gene duplication events in the same or different species). Orthologous genes in various species that arose from a common ancestor gene through speciation, and orthologs, in general, retain the same function across time. The determination of orthologs is an important step in predicting gene function in freshly sequenced genomes. Paralogs are homologs from the same species that do not catalyze the very same reaction or perform the same function.

Singletons are rare variant which carry out genetic variation through unique chromosomes. It is a kind of read in genome with a sequence that is present exactly once which become unique (drive5, Bioinformatics software and services).

Orthologous proteins, clusters and singletons among Zebra fish (*Danio rerio*), Catla (*Catla catla*), Ruhi (*Labeo rohita*), Kalibaus/Orangefin labeo (*Labeo calbasu*), Mrigal carp (*Cirrhinus cirrhosus*)

Table 17. Proteins, clusters, singletons of Indian major carps, Kalibaus and Zebra fish

Species	Proteins	Clusters	Singletons
<i>Danio rerio</i>	24544	17385	2839
<i>Catla catla</i>	49028	25860	19973
<i>Labeo rohita</i> (Halda)	47568	26142	18083
<i>Labeo calbasu</i>	68803	37749	25822
<i>Cirrhinus cirrhosus</i>	59599	37019	17873

Figure 45. Ortholog cluster proteins among compared 5 species

Figure 46. Ortholog cluster proteins (overlapped) among compared 5 species

Figure 47. Ortholog proteins among compared 5 species

Figure 48. Comparison of proteins, clusters and singletons in *Labeo rohita* from Halda River among other species

Figure 49. Ortho venn diagram indicating orthologs and unique protein clusters in *Labeo rohita* from Halda River among other species

Table 18. Chromosome wise unique genes of Halda Rohu (*L. rohita*)

Chromosome	Unique Muscle Genes
Chr1.	4
Chr2.	7
Chr3.	4
Chr4.	2
Chr5.	3
Chr6.	2
Chr7.	3
Chr8.	6
Chr9.	3
Chr10.	0
Chr11.	2
Chr12.	2
Chr13.	0
Chr14.	2
Chr15.	0
Chr16.	2
Chr17.	2
Chr18.	1
Chr19.	1
Chr20.	1
Chr21.	5
Chr22.	0
Chr23.	0
Chr24.	3
Chr25.	1

Figure 50. Visualisation of chromosome wise unique genes of *Labeo rohita* from Halda River.

Chapter 6

Discussion

6.1 Genome assembly & gene annotation

In chromosome level assembly of my study total size/number of bases of the genome found is greater than 2 other reference genome, **1,159,574,983** > 1,126,558,565 > 992,683,291 but lower than Indian CIFA Jayanti, **1,159,574,983** < 1,484,730,970. No. of sequence in my study is lower than any other reference genome **2401** < 2869 < 2870 < 13523, which indicates less fragmented better genome than others. N50 is bigger than any 2 other reference genome $37.9 \text{ mbp}^2 < \mathbf{35.5 \text{ mbp}^2} > 32.5 \text{ mbp}^2 > 1.9 \text{ mbp}^2$. L50 is smallest in my study **9**, which is better because of having large sized scaffolds in lower L50. Unplaced genes are lowest in number **2376** < 2844 < 13523.

Total BUSCO groups searched of Eukaryotes during benchmarking are 255, where 244 are complete and 11 are fragmented with no missing groups, which showed 95.7% gene completeness.

Total BUSCO groups searched of Actinopterygii during benchmarking are 3640, where 3400 are complete, 115 are fragmented and 125 groups are missing. That results in 93.5% gene completeness.

6.2 Chromosome level assembly

In genome assembly 87% genes are unique whereas 13% repeat content elements found. 47568 genes are predicted via augustus with 33342 annotated genes, while more than 19000 gene ontology found with more than 20000 pathway for protein protein relationship. In total 47568 genes **63.39%** genes are placed in chromosome, in number 30153. Where **36.61%** genes not placed in chromosome, in number 17415. **70.01%** of total genes are annotated and **29.9%** genes are non-coding, pseudogenes. Among annotated genes **71.95%** placed in chromosome and rest are unplaced. Majority of the KEGG pathways found in chromosome (**79.36%**) and very little found in unplaced genes (**20.64%**).

Among placed genes **79.5%** are annotated while more than **20%** genes are non coding and pseudogenes. Chromosome level assembly helps finding genes per chromosome and protein too. **Chr. (Chromosome) 5** has highest number of genes (**1662**), annotated gene proteins (**1323**), gene ontology (**984**), and KEGG pathway (**970**). Highest number of non-coding, pseudogenes found in **chr. 16**. **Chr. 11** has lowest number of genes (**907**) and non-coding, pseudogenes (**159**). Lowest number of annotated gene proteins (**716**) and KEGG pathway (**486**) found in **chr. 24**. Gene ontology lowest in **chr. 22** (**471**).

6.3 Comparative analysis of genome & proteome

In comparative analysis halda river ruhi has shown higher number of genes per chromosome than BAU-BD-2019 strain except **chr. 3**. Highest number of gene

variation found in **chr. 9** and **chr. 18** and lowest gene variation in **chr. 21**. Number of total genes in halda river ruhi (**47568**) is greater than refseq BAU-BD-2019 (**31731**). Total chromosome placed genes and unplaced genes in halda river ruhi is also greater than refseq.

Chr. 16 of my study has highest number of non-coding, pseudogenes (**396**) with highest variation with the refseq while lowest variation in **chr.20** as it has lowest amount of genes in **chr. 20 (167)**. Number of total non-coding,pseudogenes in halda river ruhi (**14226**) is greater than refseq BAU-BD-2019 (**5105**). Total chromosome placed non-coding genes and unplaced genes in halda river ruhi is also greater than refseq.

Halda river ruhi has shown higher number of annotated gene proteins per chromosome than BAU-BD-2019 strain in 16 chromosomes **chr. (4,5,7,8,9,10,12,13,14,15,17,18,19,20,24,25)** except 9. Highest number of annotated gene protein variation found in **chr. 9** and lowest gene protein variation in **chr. 15**. Number of total annotated gene proteins in halda river ruhi (**33342**) is greater than refseq BAU-BD-2019 (**26626**). Total chromosome placed genes and unplaced genes in halda river ruhi is also greater than refseq.

Proteins found in halda ruhi fish is greater than zebra fish (**47568 > 24544**) but lower than catla, mrigel carp and kalibaush (**47568 < 49028 < 59599 < 68803**).

Cluster proteins found in halda ruhi fish is greater than catla and zebra fish (**26142 > 25860 > 17385**) but lower than mrigel carp and kalibaush (**26142 < 37019 < 37749**).

Singletons present in halda ruhi is greater than mrigel carp and zebra fish (**18083 > 17873 > 2839**) and lower than catla and kalibaush (**18083 < 19973 < 25822**).

Among 47568 genes found in my study approximately **1010** annotated genes are protein coding and directly or indirectly responsible for muscle growth of *Labeo rohita* from halda river. According to the refseq BAU-BD-2019 approximately **82** unique genes are found in *Labeo rohita* from halda river. **29.27%** of those genes are unplaced; **24 genes**, while **70.73%** of those genes are placed in chromosome. Max. number of unique muscle genes lies in **chr. 2** indicating high degree of polymorphism and mutations while no uniqueness in chr. 10, chr. 13,22 & 23 indicates less polymorphism and mutations.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

So, after all of the above discussion and detailed study, I can conclude that Ruhi fish from halda river is more divergence and showing somewhat difference in genes, annotated proteins, pseudogenes in total and chromosome wise distribution relating to reference genome of rohu from other sources. Unique genes and proteins related to muscle growth found might cause the difference in muscle growth and texture in halda rohu compared to rohu from other locations of Bangladesh. Though further advanced and repetitive studies based on unique proteins and protein-protein interaction are needed to strengthen my study for future research purposes on IMC of Halda River.

Chapter 8

References

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Appendices

Figure 51. Computational tools used in servers with CPU usage (tblastn, augustus)

Figure 52. Display showing genome statistics of reference genome

Figure 53. Computational tools used in servers with CPU usage (tblastn, augustus)

Figure 54. Gene prediction through AUGUSTUS

Figure 55. Running several tools & commands at a glance

Figure 56. Computational tools used in servers with CPU usage (tblastn, augustus)

Augustus Command Lines

augustus --species=help to get species list

augustus --genemodel=complete --gff3=on --UTR=on --uniqueGeneId=true --species=SPECIES queryfilename > augustus.gff

zebrafish - *Danio rerio*

E_coli_K12 - Escherichia coli K12

human - *Homo sapiens*

chicken - *Gallus gallus domesticus*

UTR is not supported for all the species

getAnnoFasta.pl augustus.gff # to convert gff file to aa (amino acid)
fasta protein file

BUSCO Command Lines

busco -i [SEQUENCE_FILE] -l [LINEAGE] -o [OUTPUT_NAME] -m [MODE] [OTHER OPTIONS]

auto-lineage

Automatically select lineage (slowest)

auto-lineage-prok

Automatically select lineage as prokaryote (slow but accurate to find optimum lineage)

auto-lineage-euk

Automatically select lineage as eukaryote (slow but accurate to find optimum lineage)

Mode genome: -m geno/genome

Mode transcriptome: -m tran or transcriptome

Mode proteins: -m - prot or proteins

Force rewriting of existing files: -f, --force

Continue a run that had already partially completed: -r, --restart

AUGUSTUS to predict gene

--augustus

```
--augustus_parameters --PARAM1=VALUE1,--PARAM2=VALUE2
```

```
busco --cpu 16 -i file.fa --auto-lineage-euk -o busco -m geno/prot -f
```

```
busco --cpu 16 -i file.fa --auto-lineage-euk -o busco-augustus -m geno/prot -f --  
augustus --augustus_parameters --species=zebrafish --genemodel=complete --  
gff3=on --uniqueGeneId=true
```

```
busco --cpu 12 -i cc.chr.fa --auto-lineage-euk -o busco -m geno -f
```

```
busco --cpu 12 -i lr.chr.fa --auto-lineage-euk -o busco -m geno -f
```

```
busco --cpu 12 -i cc.chr.fa --auto-lineage-euk -o busco-augustus -m geno -f --  
augustus --augustus_species zebrafish
```

```
busco --cpu 12 -i lr.chr.fa --auto-lineage-euk -o busco-augustus -m geno -f --augustus  
--augustus_species zebrafish
```

Rui gene prediction with AUGUSTUS:

```
augustus --genemodel=complete --gff3=on --uniqueGeneId=true --species=zebrafish  
lr.chr.fa > augustus.gff
```

Rui gene benchmark with BUSCO:

```
busco --cpu 12 -i lr.chr.fa --auto-lineage-euk -o busco -m geno -f
```

Rui gene prediction + benchmark with BUSCO:

```
busco --cpu 12 -i lr.chr.fa --auto-lineage-euk -o busco-augustus -m geno -f --augustus  
--augustus_species zebrafish
```

Unique and orthologous genes (1010) responsible for the exclusive muscle growth of *Labeo rohita* from Halda river given below with their protein coding function through chromosome level assembly.

Table 19. Genes responsible for muscle growth of *L. rohita* from Halda River. (Bold names are expressing unique genes of halda rohu)

Chromosome Location	Preferred Gene Name	Gene Description
Chr1.g944.t1	APBB2	Amyloid beta (A4) precursor protein-binding, family B, member
Chr5.g5947.t1	APBA1	Amyloid beta (A4) precursor protein-binding, family A, member
Chr7.g8276.t1	APBB2	Amyloid beta (A4) precursor protein-binding, family B, member
Chr1.g1223.t1	APP	Amyloid beta (A4)
Chr2.g1420.t1	APBB2	Amyloid beta (A4) precursor protein-binding, family B, member
Chr7.g9116.t1	APBA2	Amyloid beta (A4) precursor protein-binding, family A, member
Chr9.g11797.t1	APP	Amyloid beta (A4)
Chr10.g13091.t1	-	Amyloid beta (A4) precursor protein-binding, family A, member
Chr14.g16647.t1	-	Amyloid beta A4 precursor protein-binding family B member 2-like
Chr15.g18332.t1	APPBP2	Amyloid beta precursor protein (cytoplasmic tail) binding protein 2
Chr15.g18585.t1	APLP1	Amyloid beta (A4) precursor-like protein 1
Chr18.g22541.t1	APLP2	Amyloid beta (A4) precursor-like protein 2
Chr21.g25452.t1	APBB3	Amyloid beta (A4) precursor protein-binding, family B, member
Chr25.g29452.t1	lin-10	Amyloid beta (A4) precursor protein-binding, family A, member
UN.g36065.t1	APBB1	Amyloid beta (A4) precursor protein-binding, family B, member
Chr25.g29866.t1	SAAL1	Serum amyloid A-like 1
Chr4.g4911.t1	Prl	Prolactin 2
Chr23.g27927.t1	CNTN4	Contactin 3a, tandem duplicate 1
Chr23.g27933.t1	phactr3	Phosphatase and actin regulator

Chr24.g28524.t1	-	Actinodin1
Chr25.g29775.t1	ACTC1	Actin, alpha cardiac muscle
UN.g37794.t1	CAPZB	Capping protein (actin filament) muscle Z-line, beta
Chr1.g195.t1	-	Afadin- and alpha-actinin-binding
Chr1.g244.t1	-	Actin, alpha
Chr1.g315.t1	ACTR2	Actin-related protein
Chr1.g1146.t1	FSCN1	Fascin homolog 1, actin-bundling protein a (Strongylocentrotus purpuratus)
Chr1.g1147.t1	FSCN1	Fascin homolog 1, actin-bundling protein a (Strongylocentrotus purpuratus)
Chr1.g1148.t1	ACTB	Belongs to the actin family
Chr1.g1263.t1	-	Prolactin receptor-like
Chr2.g1318.t1	PHACTR1	Phosphatase and actin regulator
Chr2.g1956.t1	xirp1	Xin actin-binding
Chr2.g2116.t1	-	Actinodin2
Chr2.g2166.t1	ASTN1	Astrotactin 1
Chr2.g2167.t1	ASTN1	Astrotactin 1
Chr2.g2483.t1	CACTIN	Conserved mid region of cactin
Chr3.g2777.t1	SLC9A3R2	Scaffold protein that connects plasma membrane proteins with members of the ezrin moesin radixin family and thereby helps to link them to the actin cytoskeleton and to regulate their surface expression
Chr3.g3000.t1	ARPC1A	Arp2/3 complex-mediated actin nucleation
Chr3.g3005.t1	FSCN1	Fascin homolog 1, actin-bundling protein a (Strongylocentrotus purpuratus)
Chr3.g3007.t1	ACTB	Belongs to the actin family
Chr3.g3068.t1	CNTNAP1	Contactin associated protein 1
Chr3.g3108.t1	DCTN5	dynactin
Chr3.g3163.t1	RPL23	cellular response to actinomycin D
Chr3.g3190.t1	NOSIP	Negatively regulates nitric oxide production by inducing nitric oxide synthase translocation to actin cytoskeleton and inhibiting its enzymatic activity
Chr3.g3200.t1	ASTN2	Astrotactin 2
Chr3.g3206.t1	prl	prolactin
Chr3.g3241.t1	-	Actinoporin-like protein

Chr3.g3629.t1	SMARCA4	SWI SNF related, matrix associated, actin dependent regulator of chromatin, subfamily a, member 4
Chr3.g3783.t1	FSCN2	Fascin homolog 2, actin-bundling protein, retinal (Strongylocentrotus purpuratus)
Chr3.g4119.t1	TRIOBP	TRIO and F-actin binding protein
Chr4.g4921.t1	cntn1	Contactin 1b
Chr4.g5002.t1	FLNC	Filamin C, gamma b (actin binding protein 280)
Chr4.g5003.t1	FLNC	Filamin C, gamma b (actin binding protein 280)
Chr5.g5530.t1	ASTN2	Astrotactin 2
Chr5.g5532.t1	ASTN2	Astrotactin 2
Chr5.g5553.t1	ASTN2	Astrotactin 2
Chr5.g5938.t1	PRLR	Prolactin receptor
Chr5.g6040.t1	SMARCA2	SWI SNF related, matrix associated, actin dependent regulator of chromatin, subfamily a, member 2
Chr5.g6192.t1	KPTN	Kaptin, actin binding protein
Chr5.g6304.t1	ARPC5L	Functions as component of the Arp2 3 complex which is involved in regulation of actin polymerization and together with an activating nucleation-promoting factor (NPF) mediates the formation of branched actin networks
Chr5.g6570.t1	SMARCA1	SWI SNF related, matrix associated, actin dependent regulator of chromatin, subfamily a, member 1
Chr6.g6983.t1	SMARCA4	SWI SNF related, matrix associated, actin dependent regulator of chromatin, subfamily a, member 4
Chr6.g7249.t1	XIRP2	Xin actin-binding repeat containing 2a
Chr6.g7250.t1	XIRP2	Xin actin-binding repeat containing 2a
Chr6.g7629.t1	ACTL6A	Actin-like
Chr6.g7797.t1	SMARCC2	SWI SNF related, matrix associated, actin dependent regulator of chromatin, subfamily c, member 2
Chr6.g7832.t1	ARPC4	Functions as actin-binding component of the Arp2 3 complex which is involved in regulation of actin polymerization and together with an activating nucleation-promoting factor (NPF) mediates the formation of branched actin networks. Seems to contact the mother actin filament

Chr6.g7911.t1	CNTN3	Contactin 6
Chr6.g7913.t1	CNTN3	Contactin 6
Chr6.g7915.t1	CNTN6	Contactin 3 (plasmacytoma associated)
Chr6.g7916.t1	CNTN4	Contactin 4
Chr6.g7940.t1	AFAP1	Actin filament associated protein 1
Chr6.g7957.t1	CAPZA1	F-actin-capping proteins bind in a Ca ²⁺ -independent manner to the fast growing ends of actin filaments (barbed end) thereby blocking the exchange of subunits at these ends. Unlike other capping proteins (such as gelsolin and severin), these proteins do not sever actin filaments
Chr6.g8013.t1	-	Actin-binding Rho activating protein a
Chr6.g8109.t1	DCTN2	Dynaactin 2 (p50)
Chr7.g8869.t1	SMARCD3	SWI SNF related, matrix associated, actin dependent regulator of chromatin, subfamily d, member 3b
Chr7.g9048.t1	CORO2A	actin filament binding
Chr7.g9611.t1	-	Actin-related protein
Chr7.g9614.t1	ACTN3	Actinin alpha
Chr7.g9780.t1	DCTN1	dynaactin
Chr8.g10119.t1	-	Actin filament-associated protein 1-like
Chr8.g10120.t1	DMTN	Dematin actin binding protein
Chr8.g10147.t1	-	Prolactin releasing hormone receptor
Chr8.g10148.t1	-	Prolactin releasing hormone receptor
Chr8.g10200.t1	ARPC5L	Functions as component of the Arp2 3 complex which is involved in regulation of actin polymerization and together with an activating nucleation-promoting factor (NPF) mediates the formation of branched actin networks
Chr8.g10357.t1	SMARCB1	SWI SNF related, matrix associated, actin dependent regulator of chromatin, subfamily b, member
Chr8.g10398.t1	SMARCAD1	SWI SNF-related, matrix-associated actin-dependent regulator of chromatin, subfamily a, containing DEAD H box

Chr8.g10436.t1	CAPZA1	F-actin-capping proteins bind in a Ca ²⁺ -independent manner to the fast growing ends of actin filaments (barbed end) thereby blocking the exchange of subunits at these ends. Unlike other capping proteins (such as gelsolin and severin), these proteins do not sever actin filaments
Chr8.g10645.t1	DCTN3	Dynactin 3 (p22)
Chr8.g10662.t1	NEXN	Nexilin (F actin binding protein)
Chr8.g10879.t1	CTTNBP2	Cortactin binding protein 2
Chr9.g11971.t1	ARPC2	Functions as actin-binding component of the Arp2/3 complex which is involved in regulation of actin polymerization and together with an activating nucleation-promoting factor (NPF) mediates the formation of branched actin networks
Chr9.g11995.t1	xirp2	Xin actin-binding
Chr9.g12128.t1	ACTR5	actin-related protein 5
Chr9.g12318.t1	-	Prolactin receptor-like
Chr10.g12347.t1	-	Actin depolymerisation factor/cofilin -like domains
Chr10.g12370.t1	-	Prolactin releasing hormone receptor
Chr10.g12497.t1	-	Somatolactin
Chr10.g12552.t1	-	actin filament reorganization
Chr10.g12847.t1	DMTN	Dematin actin binding protein
Chr10.g13284.t1	CNTN3	Contactin 6
Chr10.g13318.t1	CNTNAP4	Contactin-associated protein-like
Chr10.g13320.t1	ACTR2	Actin-related protein
Chr11.g13581.t1	TWF2	Twinfilin, actin-binding protein, homolog 2b (Drosophila)
Chr11.g13603.t1	ARPC4	Functions as actin-binding component of the Arp2/3 complex which is involved in regulation of actin polymerization and together with an activating nucleation-promoting factor (NPF) mediates the formation of branched actin networks. Seems to contact the mother actin filament

Chr11.g13711.t1	RTEL1	ATP-dependent DNA helicase implicated in telomere-length regulation, DNA repair and the maintenance of genomic stability. Acts as an anti-recombinase to counteract toxic recombination and limit crossover during meiosis. Regulates meiotic recombination and crossover homeostasis by physically dissociating strand invasion events and thereby promotes noncrossover repair by meiotic synthesis dependent strand annealing (SDSA) as well as disassembly of D loop recombination intermediates. Also disassembles T loops and prevents telomere fragility by counteracting telomeric G4-DNA structures, which together ensure the dynamics and stability of the telomere
Chr11.g13712.t1	RTEL1	ATP-dependent DNA helicase implicated in telomere-length regulation, DNA repair and the maintenance of genomic stability. Acts as an anti-recombinase to counteract toxic recombination and limit crossover during meiosis. Regulates meiotic recombination and crossover homeostasis by physically dissociating strand invasion events and thereby promotes noncrossover repair by meiotic synthesis dependent strand annealing (SDSA) as well as disassembly of D loop recombination intermediates. Also disassembles T loops and prevents telomere fragility by counteracting telomeric G4-DNA structures, which together ensure the dynamics and stability of the telomere
Chr11.g13949.t1	-	actin binding
Chr11.g14078.t1	BRK1	BRICK1, SCAR WAVE actin-nucleating complex subunit
Chr11.g14302.t1	CNTN2	Contactin 2
Chr12.g14392.t1	FMN2	actin binding
Chr12.g14408.t1	ACTN2	Actinin, alpha 2
Chr12.g14502.t1	DPYSL4	hydrolase activity, acting on carbon-nitrogen (but not peptide) bonds
Chr12.g14578.t1	FSCN2	Fascin homolog 2, actin-bundling protein, retinal (Strongylocentrotus purpuratus)

Chr12.g14662.t1	AFAP1L2	Actin filament associated protein 1-like 2
Chr12.g14664.t1	AFAP1L2	Actin filament-associated protein 1-like
Chr12.g14666.t1	ATRNL1	Attractin-like
Chr12.g14807.t1	AFAP1	Actin filament associated protein 1
Chr12.g14808.t1	ABLIM2	Actin binding LIM protein family, member 2
Chr12.g14927.t1	LIPA	hydrolase activity, acting on ester bonds
Chr13.g15664.t1	ACTR2	Actin
Chr13.g15875.t1	ATRNL1	Attractin
Chr13.g15916.t1	DCTN1	dynactin
Chr13.g15960.t1	ATRNL1	Attractin-like
Chr13.g16030.t1	PHACTR2	Phosphatase and actin regulator
Chr13.g16041.t1	ACTA1	Actin, alpha
Chr13.g16253.t1	-	Belongs to the actin-binding proteins ADF family
Chr13.g16266.t1	SLC9A3R1	Scaffold protein that connects plasma membrane proteins with members of the ezrin moesin radixin family and thereby helps to link them to the actin cytoskeleton and to regulate their surface expression
Chr13.g16306.t1	ACTN1	Actinin, alpha 1
Chr14.g16716.t1	FILIP1L	Cortactin-binding protein-2
Chr14.g16908.t1	AFAP1L1	Actin filament associated protein 1-like
Chr14.g16931.t1	-	Actin filament-associated protein 1-like
Chr14.g16960.t1	SPDL1	Required for the localization of dynein and dynactin to the mitotic kintochore. Dynein is believed to control the initial lateral interaction between the kinetochore and spindle microtubules and to facilitate the subsequent formation of end-on kinetochore-microtubule attachments mediated by the NDC80 complex

Chr14.g17111.t1	DCTN4	dynactin
Chr14.g17138.t1	cntn1	Contactin 1b
Chr14.g17589.t1	MSN	actin binding
Chr15.g18636.t1	USP16	Specifically deubiquitinates 'Lys-120' of histone H2A (H2AK119Ub), a specific tag for epigenetic transcriptional repression, thereby acting as a coactivator. Deubiquitination of histone H2A is a prerequisite for subsequent phosphorylation at 'Ser-11' of histone H3 (H3S10ph), and is required for chromosome segregation when cells enter into mitosis. Regulates Hox gene expression via histone H2A deubiquitination. Prefers nucleosomal substrates. Does not deubiquitinate histone H2B
Chr16.g18874.t1	SACM1L	SAC1 suppressor of actin mutations 1-like b (yeast)
Chr16.g18875.t1	SACM1L	SAC1 suppressor of actin mutations 1-like b (yeast)
Chr16.g18894.t1	SPIRE1	Spire-type actin nucleation factor
Chr16.g19088.t1	SMARCC1	SWI SNF related, matrix associated, actin dependent regulator of chromatin, subfamily c, member
Chr16.g19138.t1	-	Actin-binding Rho-activating protein-like
Chr16.g19234.t1	PHACTR4	Phosphatase and actin regulator
Chr16.g20161.t1	PREB	Prolactin regulatory
Chr16.g20162.t1	PREB	Prolactin regulatory
Chr17.g20348.t1	ACTA1	Actin, alpha
Chr17.g20539.t1	CFL2	Belongs to the actin-binding proteins ADF family
Chr17.g20702.t1	ACTN2	Actinin, alpha 2
Chr18.g21770.t1	COTL1	Coactosin-like F-actin binding protein 1
Chr18.g21891.t1	ACTN3	Actinin alpha
Chr18.g21923.t1	CTTNBP2	Cortactin binding protein 2

Chr18.g21929.t1	ARPIN	Actin-related protein 2 3 complex inhibitor
Chr18.g21934.t1	MACF1	Microtubule-actin cross-linking factor 1
Chr18.g22359.t1	CTTN	cortactin
Chr18.g22454.t1	-	Somatolactin
Chr18.g22570.t1	CNTN5	Contactin 5
Chr18.g22572.t1	CNTN5	Contactin 5
Chr18.g22576.t1	CNTN5	Contactin 5
Chr19.g22790.t1	-	Phosphatase and actin regulator
Chr19.g22989.t1	SACM1L	SAC1 suppressor of actin mutations 1-like a (yeast)
Chr19.g23121.t1	SPIRE1	Spire-type actin nucleation factor
Chr19.g23163.t1	MACF1	Microtubule-actin cross-linking factor 1
Chr19.g23164.t1	MACF1	Microtubule-actin cross-linking factor 1
Chr19.g23165.t1	MACF1	Microtubule-actin cross-linking factor 1
Chr19.g23167.t1	ANLN	Anillin, actin binding protein
Chr19.g23345.t1	ABRA	Actin-binding Rho activating protein b
Chr19.g23386.t1	-	SWI SNF related, matrix associated, actin dependent regulator of chromatin, subfamily c, member 1b
Chr19.g23826.t1	-	actin binding
Chr20.g23942.t1	ACTL7A	Belongs to the actin family
Chr20.g23944.t1	ACTL7A	Belongs to the actin family
Chr20.g24529.t1	-	Actin, alpha
Chr20.g24621.t1	ARPC5	Functions as component of the Arp2 3 complex which is involved in regulation of actin polymerization and together with an activating nucleation-promoting factor (NPF) mediates the formation of branched actin networks

Chr20.g24927.t1	PHACTR1	Phosphatase and actin regulator
Chr20.g24977.t1	ACTR10	Actin-related protein 10
Chr20.g24978.t1	ACTR10	Actin-related protein 10
Chr21.g25519.t1	AFAP1L1	Actin filament associated protein 1-like 1b
Chr21.g25579.t1	ACTN3	Actinin alpha
Chr21.g25859.t1	SMARCB1	SWI SNF related, matrix associated, actin dependent regulator of chromatin, subfamily b, member
Chr21.g25927.t1	PRLR	Prolactin receptor
Chr22.g26150.t1	-	barbed-end actin filament capping
Chr22.g26600.t1	HMG20B	SWI SNF-related matrix-associated actin-dependent regulator of chromatin subfamily E member
Chr22.g26993.t1	SMARCD1	SWI SNF related, matrix associated, actin dependent regulator of chromatin, subfamily d, member 1

Chr22.g27167.t1	NCBP2	<p>Component of the cap-binding complex (CBC), which binds co-transcriptionally to the 5' cap of pre-mRNAs and is involved in various processes such as pre-mRNA splicing, translation regulation, nonsense-mediated mRNA decay, RNA-mediated gene silencing (RNAi) by microRNAs (miRNAs) and mRNA export. The CBC complex is involved in mRNA export from the nucleus, leading to the recruitment of the mRNA export machinery to the 5' end of mRNA and to mRNA export in a 5' to 3' direction through the nuclear pore. The CBC complex is also involved in mediating U snRNA and intronless mRNAs export from the nucleus. The CBC complex is essential for a pioneer round of mRNA translation, before steady state translation when the CBC complex is replaced by cytoplasmic cap-binding protein eIF4E. The pioneer round of mRNA translation mediated by the CBC complex plays a central role in nonsense-mediated mRNA decay (NMD), NMD only taking place in mRNAs bound to the CBC complex, but not on eIF4E-bound mRNAs. The CBC complex enhances NMD in mRNAs containing at least one exon-junction complex (EJC), promoting the interaction between upf1 and upf2. The CBC complex is also involved in 'failsafe' NMD, which is independent of the EJC complex, while it does not participate in Staufen-mediated mRNA decay (SMD). During cell proliferation, the CBC complex is also involved in microRNAs (miRNAs) biogenesis via its interaction with srrt ars2, thereby being required for miRNA-mediated RNA interference. The CBC complex also acts as a negative regulator of parn, thereby acting as an inhibitor of mRNA deadenylation. In the CBC complex, ncbp2 cbp20 recognizes and binds capped RNAs (m7GpppG-capped RNA) but requires ncbp1 cbp80 to stabilize the movement of its N-terminal loop and lock the CBC into a high affinity cap-binding state with the cap structure. The conventional cap-binding complex with NCBP2 binds both small nuclear RNA (snRNA) and messenger (mRNA) and is involved in their export from the nucleus</p>
Chr23.g27558.t1	ACTA2	Actin, alpha
Chr23.g27618.t1	ACTR1B	ARP1 actin-related protein 1, centractin (yeast)

Chr23.g27699.t1	NEXN	Nexilin (F actin binding protein)
Chr23.g27771.t1	FLNA	Filamin A, alpha (actin binding protein 280)
Chr23.g27916.t1	-	Contactin 3a, tandem duplicate 2
Chr23.g27918.t1	-	Contactin 3a, tandem duplicate 2
Chr24.g28655.t1	-	Xin actin-binding repeat-containing protein 1-like
Chr24.g28681.t1	CNTNAP2	Contactin associated protein-like 2a
Chr24.g28682.t1	CNTNAP2	Contactin associated protein-like 2a
Chr24.g28686.t1	CNTNAP2	Contactin associated protein-like 2a
Chr24.g28925.t1	ACTR3B	ARP3 actin-related protein 3 homolog B (yeast)
Chr25.g29161.t1	FLNC	Filamin C, gamma a (actin binding protein 280)
Chr25.g29546.t1	LMOD2	pointed-end actin filament capping
Chr25.g29648.t1	ACTR6	ARP6 actin-related protein 6 homolog (yeast)
Chr25.g29950.t1	SMARCD2	SWI SNF related, matrix associated, actin dependent regulator of chromatin, subfamily d, member 2
Chr25.g30112.t1	TWF1	Twinfilin, actin-binding protein, homolog
UN.g30322.t1	CNTN1	Contactin 1
UN.g30440.t1	WHAMM	WAS protein homolog associated with actin, golgi membranes and microtubules
UN.g32292.t1	DCTN6	Dynactin
UN.g35665.t1	ACTL6B	Belongs to the actin family
UN.g35672.t1	CORO2A	actin filament binding
Chr6.g7573.t1	DZIP1L	DAZ interacting zinc finger protein 1-like
Chr7.g9138.t1	PSTPIP1	Proline-serine-threonine phosphatase interacting protein
Chr10.g13025.t1	PSTPIP2	Proline-serine-threonine phosphatase interacting protein 2

Chr14.g16691.t1	FGF1	Plays an important role in the regulation of cell survival, cell division, angiogenesis, cell differentiation and cell migration. Functions as potent mitogen in vitro. Acts as a ligand for FGFR1 and integrins. Binds to FGFR1 in the presence of heparin leading to FGFR1 dimerization and activation via sequential autophosphorylation on tyrosine residues which act as docking sites for interacting proteins, leading to the activation of several signaling cascades. Binds to integrins. Its binding to integrins and subsequent ternary complex formation with integrins and FGFR1 are essential for FGF1 signaling
Chr14.g17527.t1	RLIM	Ring finger protein, LIM domain interacting
Chr17.g20630.t1	STYX	Serine threonine tyrosine interacting protein
Chr18.g22019.t1	PSTPIP1	Proline-serine-threonine phosphatase interacting protein
Chr18.g22663.t1	PPFIBP2	Protein tyrosine phosphatase, receptor-type, F interacting protein, binding protein 2a
Chr18.g22664.t1	PPFIBP2	Protein tyrosine phosphatase, receptor-type, F interacting protein, binding protein 2a
Chr21.g25079.t1	JAKMIP2	Janus kinase and microtubule interacting protein 2
Chr25.g29748.t1	PPFIBP2	Protein tyrosine phosphatase, receptor-type, F interacting protein, binding protein
Chr1.g294.t1	CNN1	Thin filament-associated protein that is implicated in the regulation and modulation of smooth muscle contraction. It is capable of binding to actin, calmodulin, troponin C and tropomyosin. The interaction of calponin with actin inhibits the actomyosin Mg-ATPase activity
Chr2.g1869.t1	CNN3	Thin filament-associated protein that is implicated in the regulation and modulation of smooth muscle contraction. It is capable of binding to actin, calmodulin, troponin C and tropomyosin. The interaction of calponin with actin inhibits the actomyosin Mg-ATPase activity

Chr2.g1982.t1	CNN2	Thin filament-associated protein that is implicated in the regulation and modulation of smooth muscle contraction. It is capable of binding to actin, calmodulin, troponin C and tropomyosin. The interaction of calponin with actin inhibits the actomyosin Mg-ATPase activity
Chr3.g2741.t1	CNN1	Thin filament-associated protein that is implicated in the regulation and modulation of smooth muscle contraction. It is capable of binding to actin, calmodulin, troponin C and tropomyosin. The interaction of calponin with actin inhibits the actomyosin Mg-ATPase activity
Chr8.g10616.t1	MYO1F	Unconventional myosin tail, actin- and lipid-binding
Chr12.g14995.t1	BECN1	Beclin 1 (coiled-coil, myosin-like BCL2 interacting protein)
Chr12.g15255.t1	osp	Myosin phosphatase Rho-interacting protein-like isoform X1
Chr16.g19346.t1	MYRIP	Myosin VIIA and Rab interacting protein
Chr16.g19469.t1	MYLIP	Myosin regulatory light chain interacting protein
Chr19.g22968.t1	MYLIP	Myosin regulatory light chain interacting protein
Chr24.g28459.t1	CNN3	Thin filament-associated protein that is implicated in the regulation and modulation of smooth muscle contraction. It is capable of binding to actin, calmodulin, troponin C and tropomyosin. The interaction of calponin with actin inhibits the actomyosin Mg-ATPase activity
Chr24.g28820.t1	MYRIP	Myosin VIIA and Rab interacting protein
Chr7.g9504.t1	KIF7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr8.g10784.t1	SLMAP	Sarcolemma associated protein a
Chr11.g13974.t1	SLMAP	Sarcolemma associated protein a
Chr11.g14043.t1	KIF17	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
UN.g38741.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g39399.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g39654.t1	MYBPH	Myosin binding protein

UN.g39755.t1	unc-54	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g39828.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g40178.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g40286.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g40422.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g40556.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g40605.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g41029.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g41499.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g41605.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g41765.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g41779.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g41902.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g42124.t1	MYH1	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g42582.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g42595.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g42596.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g42699.t1	MYH4	Myosin, heavy chain 4, skeletal muscle
UN.g43081.t1	MYH10	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g43090.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g43138.t1	MYBPC3	Myosin binding protein C, cardiac
UN.g43491.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g43778.t1	MYH1	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g43934.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g44152.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g44190.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g44425.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g44489.t1	MYO5A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g44913.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain

UN.g45165.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g45166.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g46053.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g46915.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g46926.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g46975.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g47331.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g47413.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g47502.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr1.g358.t1	Msx3	Muscle segment homeobox C
Chr2.g1966.t1	MYH7	regulation of slow-twitch skeletal muscle fiber contraction
Chr2.g1967.t1	MYH7	regulation of slow-twitch skeletal muscle fiber contraction
Chr2.g2247.t1	CASQ1	Calsequestrin is a high-capacity, moderate affinity, calcium-binding protein and thus acts as an internal calcium store in muscle
Chr2.g2342.t1	MURC	Muscle-related coiled-coil
Chr3.g3154.t1	CACNA1A	Voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) mediate the entry of calcium ions into excitable cells and are also involved in a variety of calcium-dependent processes, including muscle contraction, hormone or neurotransmitter release, gene expression, cell motility, cell division and cell death. The isoform alpha-1A gives rise to P and or Q-type calcium currents. P Q-type calcium channels belong to the 'high-voltage activated' (HVA) group and are blocked by the funnel toxin (Ftx) and by the omega-agatoxin- IVA (omega-Aga-IVA). They are however insensitive to dihydropyridines (DHP), and omega-conotoxin-GVIA (omega-CTx-GVIA)

Chr3.g3301.t1	CACNA1I	Voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) mediate the entry of calcium ions into excitable cells and are also involved in a variety of calcium-dependent processes, including muscle contraction, hormone or neurotransmitter release, gene expression, cell motility, cell division and cell death. This channel gives rise to T-type calcium currents. T-type calcium channels belong to the low-voltage activated (LVA) group and are strongly blocked by nickel and mibefradil. A particularity of this type of channels is an opening at quite negative potentials, and a voltage-dependent inactivation. T-type channels serve pacemaking functions in both central neurons and cardiac nodal cells and support calcium signaling in secretory cells and vascular smooth muscle. They may also be involved in the modulation of firing patterns of neurons which is important for information processing as well as in cell growth processes
Chr4.g4660.t1	-	Troponin I, slow skeletal muscle-like
Chr5.g6368.t1	-	Voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) mediate the entry of calcium ions into excitable cells and are also involved in a variety of calcium-dependent processes, including muscle contraction, hormone or neurotransmitter release, gene expression, cell motility, cell division and cell death. The isoform alpha-1B gives rise to N-type calcium currents. N-type calcium channels belong to the 'high-voltage activated' (HVA) group and are blocked by omega-conotoxin-GVIA (omega-CTx-GVIA) and by omega-agatoxin-IIIa (omega-Aga-IIIa). They are however insensitive to dihydropyridines (DHP), and omega-agatoxin-IVA (omega-Aga-IVA). Calcium channels containing alpha-1B subunit may play a role in directed migration of immature neurons
Chr6.g7384.t1	CACNG1	This protein is a subunit of the dihydropyridine (DHP) sensitive calcium channel. Plays a role in excitation-contraction coupling. The skeletal muscle DHP-sensitive Ca(2+) channel may function only as a multiple subunit complex
Chr7.g9324.t1	CHRNB1	Cholinergic receptor, nicotinic, beta 1 (muscle) like

Chr7.g9325.t1	CHRNB1	Cholinergic receptor, nicotinic, beta 1 (muscle)
Chr8.g10128.t1	-	Voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) mediate the entry of calcium ions into excitable cells and are also involved in a variety of calcium-dependent processes, including muscle contraction, hormone or neurotransmitter release, gene expression, cell motility, cell division and cell death. The isoform alpha-1C gives rise to L-type calcium currents. Long-lasting (L-type) calcium channels belong to the 'high-voltage activated' (HVA) group. They are blocked by dihydropyridines (DHP), phenylalkylamines, benzothiazepines, and by omega-agatoxin-IIIa (omega-Aga-IIIa). They are however insensitive to omega-conotoxin-GVIA (omega-CTx-GVIA) and omega-agatoxin-IVA (omega-Aga-IVA). Calcium channels containing the alpha-1C subunit play an important role in excitation-contraction coupling in the heart. Binding of calmodulin or CABP1 at the same regulatory sites results in an opposite effects on the channel function
Chr8.g10469.t1	CACNA1S	Voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) mediate the entry of calcium ions into excitable cells and are also involved in a variety of calcium-dependent processes, including muscle contraction, hormone or neurotransmitter release, gene expression, cell motility, cell division and cell death. The isoform alpha-1C gives rise to L-type calcium currents. Long-lasting (L-type) calcium channels belong to the 'high-voltage activated' (HVA) group. They are blocked by dihydropyridines (DHP), phenylalkylamines, benzothiazepines, and by omega-agatoxin-IIIa (omega-Aga-IIIa). They are however insensitive to omega-conotoxin-GVIA (omega-CTx-GVIA) and omega-agatoxin-IVA (omega-Aga-IVA). Calcium channels containing the alpha-1C subunit play an important role in excitation-contraction coupling in the heart. Binding of calmodulin or CABP1 at the same regulatory sites results in an opposite effects on the channel function

Chr8.g10556.t1	CACNA1F	Voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) mediate the entry of calcium ions into excitable cells and are also involved in a variety of calcium-dependent processes, including muscle contraction, hormone or neurotransmitter release, gene expression, cell motility, cell division and cell death. The isoform alpha-1C gives rise to L-type calcium currents. Long-lasting (L-type) calcium channels belong to the 'high-voltage activated' (HVA) group. They are blocked by dihydropyridines (DHP), phenylalkylamines, benzothiazepines, and by omega-agatoxin-IIIa (omega-Aga-IIIa). They are however insensitive to omega-conotoxin-GVIA (omega-CTx-GVIA) and omega-agatoxin-IVA (omega-Aga-IVA). Calcium channels containing the alpha-1C subunit play an important role in excitation-contraction coupling in the heart. Binding of calmodulin or CABP1 at the same regulatory sites results in an opposite effects on the channel function
Chr9.g11886.t1	SPEG	Striated muscle preferentially expressed protein kinase-like
Chr11.g13947.t1	ACYP2	Acylphosphatase 2, muscle type
Chr12.g14709.t1	CACNA1G	Voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) mediate the entry of calcium ions into excitable cells and are also involved in a variety of calcium-dependent processes, including muscle contraction, hormone or neurotransmitter release, gene expression, cell motility, cell division and cell death. This channel gives rise to T-type calcium currents. T-type calcium channels belong to the low-voltage activated (LVA) group and are strongly blocked by nickel and mibefradil. A particularity of this type of channels is an opening at quite negative potentials, and a voltage-dependent inactivation. T-type channels serve pacemaking functions in both central neurons and cardiac nodal cells and support calcium signaling in secretory cells and vascular smooth muscle. They may also be involved in the modulation of firing patterns of neurons which is important for information processing as well as in cell growth processes

Chr14.g16819.t1	MBNL3	Muscleblind-like 3 (Drosophila)
Chr16.g19351.t1	TMOD4	Tropomodulin 4 (muscle)
Chr16.g19417.t1	gem	GTP binding protein overexpressed in skeletal muscle
Chr17.g20720.t1	ANK3	positive regulation of membrane depolarization during cardiac muscle cell action potential
Chr17.g21504.t1	MEIS2	regulation of cardiac muscle myoblast proliferation
Chr18.g21741.t1	RHOA	positive regulation of vascular smooth muscle contraction
Chr19.g23286.t1	FABP3	Fatty acid binding protein 3, muscle and heart
Chr20.g24137.t1	ACTA1	skeletal muscle fiber adaptation
Chr21.g25205.t1	MSX2	Muscle segment homeobox
Chr21.g25870.t1	-	Voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) mediate the entry of calcium ions into excitable cells and are also involved in a variety of calcium-dependent processes, including muscle contraction, hormone or neurotransmitter release, gene expression, cell motility, cell division and cell death. The isoform alpha-1B gives rise to N-type calcium currents. N-type calcium channels belong to the 'high-voltage activated' (HVA) group and are blocked by omega-conotoxin-GVIA (omega-CTx-GVIA) and by omega-agatoxin-III (omega-Aga-III). They are however insensitive to dihydropyridines (DHP), and omega-agatoxin-IVA (omega-Aga-IVA). Calcium channels containing alpha-1B subunit may play a role in directed migration of immature neurons
Chr21.g26025.t1	ATP5A1	ATP synthase, H transporting, mitochondrial F1 complex, alpha subunit 1, cardiac muscle
Chr24.g28413.t1	MURC	Muscle-related coiled-coil
Chr24.g28537.t1	SMPX	Small muscle protein, X-linked
Chr25.g29628.t1	-	Troponin I, slow skeletal muscle-like
UN.g30452.t1	Nrk1	Muscle-specific beta 1 integrin binding protein 2

UN.g32702.t1	RHOC	skeletal muscle satellite cell migration
UN.g34453.t1	PCSK5	positive regulation of smooth muscle cell-matrix adhesion
UN.g35478.t1	MBNL2	muscleblind-like
UN.g35656.t1	ENO3	Enolase 3, (beta, muscle)
UN.g36005.t1	CACNA1S	Voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) mediate the entry of calcium ions into excitable cells and are also involved in a variety of calcium-dependent processes, including muscle contraction, hormone or neurotransmitter release, gene expression, cell motility, cell division and cell death. The isoform alpha-1C gives rise to L-type calcium currents. Long-lasting (L-type) calcium channels belong to the 'high-voltage activated' (HVA) group. They are blocked by dihydropyridines (DHP), phenylalkylamines, benzothiazepines, and by omega-agatoxin-IIIa (omega-Aga-IIIa). They are however insensitive to omega-conotoxin-GVIA (omega-CTx-GVIA) and omega-agatoxin-IVA (omega-Aga-IVA). Calcium channels containing the alpha-1C subunit play an important role in excitation-contraction coupling in the heart. Binding of calmodulin or CABP1 at the same regulatory sites results in an opposite effects on the channel function
UN.g36448.t1	MYH7	regulation of slow-twitch skeletal muscle fiber contraction
UN.g36813.t1	MYH6	regulation of slow-twitch skeletal muscle fiber contraction
UN.g39825.t1	MYH6	regulation of slow-twitch skeletal muscle fiber contraction
UN.g43742.t1	MYH7	regulation of slow-twitch skeletal muscle fiber contraction
UN.g44146.t1	RHOA	skeletal muscle satellite cell migration
UN.g44237.t1	MYH7	regulation of slow-twitch skeletal muscle fiber contraction
UN.g45488.t1	MYH7	regulation of slow-twitch skeletal muscle fiber contraction
Chr1.g241.t1	DLL1	Delta-like protein
Chr1.g1008.t1	FGF20	fibroblast growth factor
Chr1.g1166.t1	NRP2	Belongs to the neuropilin family
Chr1.g1167.t1	NRP2	Belongs to the neuropilin family

Chr1.g1168.t1	NRP2	Belongs to the neuropilin family
Chr2.g1538.t1	DDR2	Discoidin domain receptor tyrosine kinase 2b
Chr2.g1708.t1	FGF12	fibroblast growth factor
Chr2.g2005.t1	GHSR	Growth hormone secretagogue receptor
Chr2.g2338.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr2.g2574.t1	LPL	The primary function of this lipase is the hydrolysis of triglycerides of circulating chylomicrons and very low density lipoproteins (VLDL). Binding to heparin sulfate proteoglycans at the cell surface is vital to the function. The apolipoprotein, APOC2, acts as a coactivator of LPL activity in the presence of lipids on the luminal surface of vascular endothelium
Chr3.g2798.t1	HGS	Hepatocyte growth factor-regulated tyrosine kinase substrate
Chr3.g2844.t1	-	Peripheral myelin protein
Chr3.g2851.t1	AATK	Apoptosis-associated tyrosine kinase a
Chr3.g2919.t1	TYK2	tyrosine kinase 2
Chr3.g3403.t1	eps811	Epidermal growth factor receptor kinase substrate 8-like protein
Chr3.g3553.t1	ADSL	Adenylosuccinate lyase
Chr3.g3555.t1	ADSL	Adenylosuccinate lyase
Chr3.g3704.t1	LMTK2	Lemur tyrosine kinase 2
Chr4.g4621.t1	CELSR3	Cadherin EGF LAG seven-pass G-type receptor
Chr4.g5108.t1	VEGFA	Vascular endothelial growth factor
Chr4.g5114.t1	FGF6	fibroblast growth factor
Chr4.g5115.t1	FGF23	Fibroblast growth factor 23
Chr4.g5204.t1	FRS2	fibroblast growth factor receptor substrate
Chr5.g5619.t1	ABL1	C-abl oncogene 1, receptor tyrosine kinase
Chr5.g5713.t1	NTRK2	Neurotrophic tyrosine kinase, receptor, type 2b
Chr5.g6136.t1	FGF5	fibroblast growth factor
Chr5.g6965.t1	TEK	Tyrosine kinase
Chr6.g7223.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr6.g7690.t1	TIE1	Endothelium-specific receptor tyrosine kinase 1
Chr6.g7698.t1	LRP8	Low density lipoprotein receptor-related protein 8, apolipoprotein e receptor
Chr6.g7704.t1	DDR2	Discoidin domain receptor tyrosine kinase 2a

Chr6.g7879.t1	MST1R	Macrophage stimulating 1 receptor (c-met-related tyrosine kinase)
Chr6.g8042.t1	MST1	Macrophage stimulating 1 (hepatocyte growth factor-like)
Chr1.g318.t1	KIF16B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr1.g1080.t1	KIF19	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr1.g1243.t1	CENPE	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr2.g1370.t1	MYLK4	Myosin light chain kinase
Chr2.g1405.t1	myl3	Myosin light chain
Chr2.g1906.t1	KIF1A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr2.g2098.t1	MYL12B	Myosin, light chain 12, genome duplicate
Chr2.g2154.t1	kif2c	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr2.g2223.t1	MYO9B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr2.g2352.t1	myo10	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr3.g3023.t1	MYO15A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr3.g3073.t1	MYH11	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr3.g3174.t1	MYLFP	Myosin light chain, phosphorylatable, fast skeletal muscle
Chr3.g3233.t1	-	Myosin, light chain kinase
Chr3.g3265.t1	MYBPC2	Myosin binding protein C, fast type a
Chr3.g3404.t1	MPRIP	Myosin phosphatase
Chr3.g3500.t1	myl4	Myosin, light
Chr3.g3669.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
Chr3.g3930.t1	myh9	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr4.g4823.t1	MYBPC1	Myosin binding protein C, slow type
Chr4.g5083.t1	KIF21A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr5.g5429.t1	KIF1C	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr5.g5566.t1	MYL3	Myosin, light
Chr5.g5880.t1	MYL3	Myosin, light

Chr5.g6295.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
Chr5.g6296.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
Chr5.g6298.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
Chr5.g6306.t1	MYO1H	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr5.g6315.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
Chr5.g6451.t1	-	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr5.g6628.t1	MYO1H	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr5.g6630.t1	MYO1H	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr5.g6878.t1	MYO19	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr5.g6909.t1	MYL2	Myosin, light chain 2, regulatory, cardiac, slow
Chr6.g7061.t1	MYL9	Myosin, light chain 9b, regulatory
Chr6.g7175.t1	MYH10	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr6.g7180.t1	-	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr6.g7197.t1	MYH11	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr6.g7270.t1	-	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr6.g7313.t1	MYLK	myosin light chain kinase
Chr6.g7587.t1	KIF1A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr6.g7588.t1	KIF1A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr6.g7603.t1	myo7b	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr6.g7830.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
Chr6.g7831.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
Chr6.g8066.t1	MYBPH	Myosin binding protein
Chr6.g8108.t1	KIF5A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr7.g8240.t1	MYL12B	Myosin, light chain 12, genome duplicate
Chr7.g8417.t1	MYO9A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr7.g8427.t1	-	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family

Chr7.g8498.t1	-	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr7.g8861.t1	MYLK3	Myosin light chain kinase 3
Chr7.g8878.t1	KIF9	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr7.g8993.t1	-	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr7.g9097.t1	KIF18A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr7.g9100.t1	MYBPC3	Myosin binding protein C, cardiac
Chr7.g9101.t1	MYBPC3	Myosin binding protein C, cardiac
Chr7.g9120.t1	myo1e	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr7.g9142.t1	TPM1	Tropomyosin like
Chr8.g10219.t1	MYL7	Myosin regulatory light chain 2, atrial
Chr8.g10770.t1	KIF2A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr8.g10791.t1	ATP2A2	Sarcoplasmic endoplasmic reticulum calcium ATPase
Chr9.g11135.t1	MYLK	myosin light chain kinase
Chr9.g11138.t1	MYO3B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr9.g11243.t1	MYO1B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr9.g11416.t1	-	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr9.g11547.t1	KIF5C	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr9.g11548.t1	KIF5C	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr9.g11850.t1	MYL1	Myosin, light chain 1
Chr9.g12147.t1	KIF5A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr10.g12448.t1	MYO18A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr10.g12449.t1	MYO18A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr10.g12450.t1	MYO18A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr10.g12567.t1	myl10	Myosin, light chain 10, regulatory

Chr10.g13328.t1	-	Myosin. Large ATPases.
Chr10.g13385.t1	KIF2A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr10.g13428.t1	MYO18B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr11.g13501.t1	KIF21B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr11.g13502.t1	KIF21B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr11.g13973.t1	SLMAP	Sarcolemma associated protein a
Chr11.g14270.t1	MYH7B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr11.g14271.t1	MYH8	Myosin N-terminal SH3-like domain
Chr12.g14505.t1	KIF5B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr12.g14593.t1	myo15b	Unconventional myosin-XV-like
Chr12.g14693.t1	MYO1D	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr12.g14937.t1	KIF20B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr12.g15197.t1	KIF22	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr12.g15246.t1	unc-15	Myosin, heavy chain
Chr14.g16697.t1	KIF3A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr15.g18333.t1	MYO18A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr15.g18334.t1	MYO18A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr15.g18378.t1	LRRC16A	Capping protein regulator and myosin 1 linker 1
Chr15.g18430.t1	MYO1C	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr16.g18883.t1	KIF13A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr16.g18884.t1	KIF13A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr16.g19185.t1	-	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family

Chr16.g19685.t1	KIFC2	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr16.g19754.t1	-	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr16.g19920.t1	LRRC16A	Capping protein regulator and myosin 1 linker 1
Chr17.g20411.t1	KIF15	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr17.g20567.t1	KIF26B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr17.g20568.t1	KIF26B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr17.g20653.t1	KIF13B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr17.g20691.t1	KIF11	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr17.g20782.t1	KIF20B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr17.g20932.t1	EPB41L4A	actomyosin structure organization
Chr17.g21053.t1	MYO6	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr17.g21054.t1	MYO6	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr17.g21059.t1	-	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr17.g21123.t1	KIF26A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr17.g21280.t1	KIF6	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr17.g21282.t1	KIF6	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr18.g21614.t1	MYO7A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr18.g21615.t1	MYO7A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr18.g21864.t1	KIF5C	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr18.g21909.t1	KIF23	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr18.g22280.t1	MYBPC2	Myosin binding protein C, fast type b
Chr18.g22508.t1	KIFC3	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family

Chr18.g22641.t1	MYO5A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr19.g22925.t1	MYO1G	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr19.g23469.t1	-	Tropomyosin
Chr20.g24462.t1	MYLK4	Myosin light chain kinase family, member
Chr20.g24486.t1	KIF26A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr20.g24555.t1	KIF25	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr20.g24847.t1	KIF3C	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr20.g24879.t1	KIF13B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr20.g24950.t1	Mhc2	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr21.g25053.t1	KIF20A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr21.g25054.t1	KIF20A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr21.g25368.t1	KIF4A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr21.g25718.t1	MYO5B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr21.g25724.t1	MYO7A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr21.g25725.t1	MYO7A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr21.g26098.t1	-	Myosin tail
Chr22.g26542.t1	KIF14	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr22.g26729.t1	TPM4	Belongs to the tropomyosin family
Chr22.g27075.t1	MYO9B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr23.g27286.t1	MYL9	Myosin, light chain 9b, regulatory
Chr23.g27510.t1	MYLK2	Myosin light chain kinase 2
Chr23.g27566.t1	KIF1C	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family

Chr23.g27567.t1	KIF1B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr23.g27583.t1	MYL6B	Myosin, light
Chr23.g27781.t1	-	Sarcolemma associated protein b
Chr23.g27808.t1	MYH7B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr23.g27857.t1	KIF3B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr23.g27989.t1	-	positive regulation of myosin-light-chain-phosphatase activity
Chr23.g27995.t1	MYBPH	Myosin binding protein
Chr24.g28261.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr24.g28262.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr24.g28300.t1	MPRIP	Myosin phosphatase
Chr24.g28370.t1	mylk	Myosin, light chain kinase
Chr24.g28962.t1	MYO3A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr24.g28963.t1	MYO3A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr25.g29184.t1	KIF15	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr25.g29224.t1	KIF21A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
Chr25.g29474.t1	TPM1	Tropomyosin 1 (alpha)
Chr25.g29884.t1	MYO5A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr25.g29885.t1	MYO5A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr25.g29965.t1	MYO5C	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr25.g30100.t1	MYO9A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
Chr25.g30102.t1	TPM2	Belongs to the tropomyosin family
UN.g30364.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g30366.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain

UN.g30369.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g30370.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g30396.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g30397.t1	MYH1	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g31883.t1	KIF5B	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
UN.g32139.t1	MYH7	Myosin. Large ATPases.
UN.g32140.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g35071.t1	MYO6	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g35664.t1	KIF1C	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Kinesin family
UN.g36103.t1	MYO15A	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g36250.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g36281.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g36390.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g36418.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g36499.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g36504.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g36564.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g36651.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g36835.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g37049.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g37311.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g37419.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g37521.t1	MYH4	Myosin, heavy chain 4, skeletal muscle
UN.g37557.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g37561.t1	MYH7	Myosin. Large ATPases.
UN.g37596.t1	unc-54	Myosin N-terminal SH3-like domain
UN.g37739.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like

UN.g37772.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g37814.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g37899.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g37900.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g37909.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g37992.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g38114.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g38314.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g38463.t1	MYH1	Myosin. Large ATPases.
UN.g38504.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g38523.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g38580.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g38588.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g38590.t1	unc-15	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g38695.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g38700.t1	MYH4	Myosin tail
UN.g38726.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g38780.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g38842.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g38904.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g39095.t1	MYH13	Myosin N-terminal SH3-like domain
UN.g39603.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g40209.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g40227.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g40239.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g40381.t1	MYH7	Myosin. Large ATPases.
UN.g40810.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g40948.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g41129.t1	-	Myosin, heavy chain 13, skeletal muscle

UN.g41236.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g41319.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g41400.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g41401.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g41584.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g42158.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g42310.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g42443.t1	MYBPC2	Myosin binding protein C, fast type b
UN.g42793.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g42811.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g43686.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g43709.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g44267.t1	MYH1	Myosin. Large ATPases.
UN.g44372.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g44491.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g44515.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g44744.t1	MYH7	Myosin. Large ATPases.
UN.g44925.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g45447.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g45472.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g45538.t1	-	Myosin heavy chain, fast skeletal muscle-like
UN.g46434.t1	MYH7	Belongs to the TRAFAC class myosin-kinesin ATPase superfamily. Myosin family
UN.g46519.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
UN.g47037.t1	MYH1	Myosin, heavy chain
Chr1.g202.t1	MB	Serves as a reserve supply of oxygen and facilitates the movement of oxygen within muscles
Chr1.g203.t1	MB	Serves as a reserve supply of oxygen and facilitates the movement of oxygen within muscles
Chr2.g2447.t1	MBNL1	muscleblind-like

Chr3.g3359.t1	ATP2A1	ATPase, Ca transporting, cardiac muscle, fast twitch 1
Chr4.g4749.t1	CACNA1C	Voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) mediate the entry of calcium ions into excitable cells and are also involved in a variety of calcium-dependent processes, including muscle contraction, hormone or neurotransmitter release, gene expression, cell motility, cell division and cell death. The isoform alpha-1C gives rise to L-type calcium currents. Long-lasting (L-type) calcium channels belong to the 'high-voltage activated' (HVA) group. They are blocked by dihydropyridines (DHP), phenylalkylamines, benzothiazepines, and by omega-agatoxin-III A (omega-Aga-III A). They are however insensitive to omega-conotoxin- GVIA (omega-CTx-GVIA) and omega-agatoxin-IVA (omega-Aga-IVA). Calcium channels containing the alpha-1C subunit play an important role in excitation-contraction coupling in the heart. Binding of calmodulin or CABP1 at the same regulatory sites results in an opposite effects on the channel function
Chr5.g6367.t1	-	Voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) mediate the entry of calcium ions into excitable cells and are also involved in a variety of calcium-dependent processes, including muscle contraction, hormone or neurotransmitter release, gene expression, cell motility, cell division and cell death. The isoform alpha-1B gives rise to N-type calcium currents. N-type calcium channels belong to the 'high-voltage activated' (HVA) group and are blocked by omega-conotoxin-GVIA (omega-CTx-GVIA) and by omega-agatoxin-III A (omega-Aga-III A). They are however insensitive to dihydropyridines (DHP), and omega-agatoxin-IVA (omega-Aga-IVA). Calcium channels containing alpha-1B subunit may play a role in directed migration of immature neurons
Chr5.g6659.t1	LMOD1	Leiomodin 1 (smooth muscle)

Chr6.g7027.t1	CACNA1I	Voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) mediate the entry of calcium ions into excitable cells and are also involved in a variety of calcium-dependent processes, including muscle contraction, hormone or neurotransmitter release, gene expression, cell motility, cell division and cell death. This channel gives rise to T-type calcium currents. T-type calcium channels belong to the low-voltage activated (LVA) group and are strongly blocked by nickel and mibefradil. A particularity of this type of channels is an opening at quite negative potentials, and a voltage-dependent inactivation. T-type channels serve pacemaking functions in both central neurons and cardiac nodal cells and support calcium signaling in secretory cells and vascular smooth muscle. They may also be involved in the modulation of firing patterns of neurons which is important for information processing as well as in cell growth processes
Chr7.g8767.t1	PAMR1	Peptidase domain containing associated with muscle regeneration 1
Chr8.g9837.t1	CACNA1D	Voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) mediate the entry of calcium ions into excitable cells and are also involved in a variety of calcium-dependent processes, including muscle contraction, hormone or neurotransmitter release, gene expression, cell motility, cell division and cell death. The isoform alpha-1C gives rise to L-type calcium currents. Long-lasting (L-type) calcium channels belong to the 'high-voltage activated' (HVA) group. They are blocked by dihydropyridines (DHP), phenylalkylamines, benzothiazepines, and by omega-agatoxin-IIIa (omega-Aga-IIIa). They are however insensitive to omega-conotoxin-GVIA (omega-CTx-GVIA) and omega-agatoxin-IVA (omega-Aga-IVA). Calcium channels containing the alpha-1C subunit play an important role in excitation-contraction coupling in the heart. Binding of calmodulin or CABP1 at the same regulatory sites results in an opposite effects on the channel function

Chr8.g9838.t1	CACNA1D	Voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) mediate the entry of calcium ions into excitable cells and are also involved in a variety of calcium-dependent processes, including muscle contraction, hormone or neurotransmitter release, gene expression, cell motility, cell division and cell death. The isoform alpha-1C gives rise to L-type calcium currents. Long-lasting (L-type) calcium channels belong to the 'high-voltage activated' (HVA) group. They are blocked by dihydropyridines (DHP), phenylalkylamines, benzothiazepines, and by omega-agatoxin-IIIa (omega-Aga-IIIa). They are however insensitive to omega-conotoxin-GVIA (omega-CTx-GVIA) and omega-agatoxin-IVA (omega-Aga-IVA). Calcium channels containing the alpha-1C subunit play an important role in excitation-contraction coupling in the heart. Binding of calmodulin or CABP1 at the same regulatory sites results in an opposite effects on the channel function
Chr8.g10425.t1	LMOD1	Leiomodin 1 (smooth muscle)
Chr9.g11642.t1	MRAS	Muscle RAS oncogene homolog
Chr9.g11887.t1	SPEG	Striated muscle preferentially expressed protein kinase-like
Chr10.g13141.t1	MUSK	Muscle, skeletal, receptor

Chr11.g14060.t1	CACNA1D	Voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) mediate the entry of calcium ions into excitable cells and are also involved in a variety of calcium-dependent processes, including muscle contraction, hormone or neurotransmitter release, gene expression, cell motility, cell division and cell death. The isoform alpha-1C gives rise to L-type calcium currents. Long-lasting (L-type) calcium channels belong to the 'high-voltage activated' (HVA) group. They are blocked by dihydropyridines (DHP), phenylalkylamines, benzothiazepines, and by omega-agatoxin-IIIa (omega-Aga-IIIa). They are however insensitive to omega-conotoxin-GVIA (omega-CTx-GVIA) and omega-agatoxin-IVA (omega-Aga-IVA). Calcium channels containing the alpha-1C subunit play an important role in excitation-contraction coupling in the heart. Binding of calmodulin or CABP1 at the same regulatory sites results in an opposite effects on the channel function
Chr12.g15146.t1	ANK3	positive regulation of membrane depolarization during cardiac muscle cell action potential
Chr13.g16053.t1	Msx3	Muscle segment homeobox C
Chr14.g16699.t1	MSX2	Muscle segment homeobox
Chr17.g20414.t1	ENO3	Enolase 3, (beta, muscle)
Chr21.g25641.t1	PHKG1	Phosphorylase kinase, gamma 1a (muscle)
Chr21.g25869.t1	CACNA1A	Voltage-sensitive calcium channels (VSCC) mediate the entry of calcium ions into excitable cells and are also involved in a variety of calcium-dependent processes, including muscle contraction, hormone or neurotransmitter release, gene expression, cell motility, cell division and cell death. The isoform alpha-1A gives rise to P and or Q-type calcium currents. P Q-type calcium channels belong to the 'high-voltage activated' (HVA) group and are blocked by the funnel toxin (Ftx) and by the omega-agatoxin-IVA (omega-Aga-IVA). They are however insensitive to dihydropyridines (DHP), and omega-conotoxin-GVIA (omega-CTx-GVIA)

UN.g32759.t1	CASQ2	Calsequestrin is a high-capacity, moderate affinity, calcium-binding protein and thus acts as an internal calcium store in muscle
UN.g32766.t1	MRAS	Muscle RAS oncogene homolog
UN.g35331.t1	PAMR1	Peptidase domain containing associated with muscle regeneration 1
UN.g35333.t1	PAMR1	Peptidase domain containing associated with muscle regeneration 1
UN.g35928.t1	casq1	Calsequestrin is a high-capacity, moderate affinity, calcium-binding protein and thus acts as an internal calcium store in muscle
UN.g37217.t1	MYH6	visceral muscle development
UN.g38697.t1	MYH7	regulation of slow-twitch skeletal muscle fiber contraction
UN.g39806.t1	MYH7	regulation of slow-twitch skeletal muscle fiber contraction
UN.g44400.t1	MYH7	regulation of slow-twitch skeletal muscle fiber contraction
UN.g45475.t1	Myh6	regulation of slow-twitch skeletal muscle fiber contraction
UN.g46287.t1	MYH6	regulation of slow-twitch skeletal muscle fiber contraction
Chr1.g514.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr1.g518.t1	LRPAP1	Low density lipoprotein receptor-related protein associated protein 1
Chr1.g555.t1	VEGFC	Vascular endothelial growth factor
Chr2.g1643.t1	EGFR	Epidermal growth factor receptor
Chr2.g2367.t1	-	Belongs to the neuropilin family
Chr2.g2578.t1	eps1511	epidermal growth factor receptor
Chr3.g2918.t1	TYK2	tyrosine kinase 2
Chr3.g3025.t1	CACNA1H	Voltage-dependent T-type calcium channel subunit
Chr3.g3207.t1	BRSK1	Protein tyrosine kinase
Chr3.g3278.t1	FGF21	fibroblast growth factor
Chr3.g3609.t1	NTN1	Laminin-type epidermal growth factor-like domain
Chr3.g4020.t1	NTRK3	Neurotrophic tyrosine kinase, receptor, type
Chr4.g4626.t1	CELSR1	Cadherin EGF LAG seven-pass G-type receptor
Chr4.g4629.t1	CELSR1	Cadherin EGF LAG seven-pass G-type receptor

Chr4.g5254.t1	EPS8	Epidermal growth factor receptor pathway substrate 8
Chr6.g7064.t1	SH3BP5L	negative regulation of protein tyrosine kinase activity
Chr6.g7822.t1	FRS3	Fibroblast growth factor receptor substrate 3
Chr7.g8354.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr7.g8391.t1	FGF4	fibroblast growth factor
Chr7.g8392.t1	FGF3	fibroblast growth factor
Chr7.g8857.t1	NETO2	Neuropilin (NRP) and tolloid (TLL)-like
Chr7.g8904.t1	IBTK	protein tyrosine kinase inhibitor activity
Chr7.g9136.t1	ALPK3	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr7.g9326.t1	FGF11	fibroblast growth factor
Chr7.g9330.t1	FGF11	fibroblast growth factor
Chr7.g9498.t1	NTRK3	Neurotrophic tyrosine kinase, receptor, type
Chr8.g9965.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr8.g10000.t1	NTRK2	Neurotrophic tyrosine kinase, receptor, type 2a
Chr8.g10046.t1	FGFR1	Fibroblast growth factor receptor
Chr8.g10047.t1	FGFR1	Fibroblast growth factor receptor
Chr8.g10087.t1	FGF17	Fibroblast growth factor
Chr8.g10198.t1	MEGF9	Multiple epidermal growth factor-like domains protein
Chr8.g10342.t1	GHR	growth hormone receptor
Chr8.g10456.t1	CELSR3	Cadherin EGF LAG seven-pass G-type receptor
Chr8.g10457.t1	CELSR3	Cadherin EGF LAG seven-pass G-type receptor
Chr8.g10486.t1	EPS8L3	Epidermal growth factor receptor kinase substrate 8-like
Chr8.g10510.t1	FRS2	fibroblast growth factor receptor substrate
Chr8.g10547.t1	PTK6	PTK6 protein tyrosine kinase
Chr8.g10702.t1	EPS15	Epidermal growth factor receptor
Chr9.g11386.t1	NRP2	Belongs to the neuropilin family
Chr9.g11388.t1	NRP2	Belongs to the neuropilin family
Chr9.g11389.t1	NRP2	Belongs to the neuropilin family
Chr10.g12341.t1	FGFR1	Fibroblast growth factor receptor
Chr10.g12563.t1	TEX14	Protein tyrosine kinase

Chr10.g12667.t1	FGF13	Fibroblast growth factor
Chr10.g13092.t1	MAMDC2	Domain in meprin, A5, receptor protein tyrosine phosphatase mu (and others)
Chr10.g13094.t1	MAMDC2	Domain in meprin, A5, receptor protein tyrosine phosphatase mu (and others)
Chr10.g13188.t1	SYK	Spleen tyrosine kinase
Chr11.g13544.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr11.g13990.t1	megf6	Multiple epidermal growth factor-like domains protein
Chr11.g14085.t1	MST1R	Macrophage stimulating 1 receptor (c-met-related tyrosine kinase)
Chr12.g14480.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr12.g14533.t1	PMP22	Peripheral myelin protein
Chr12.g14555.t1	AATK	Apoptosis-associated tyrosine kinase b
Chr12.g15286.t1	SSTR2	Somatostatin receptor
Chr12.g15287.t1	-	Somatostatin receptor type
Chr12.g15350.t1	TAOK2	Protein tyrosine kinase
Chr13.g15681.t1	DLK2	Delta-like 2 homolog (Drosophila)
Chr13.g15887.t1	FGFR3	Fibroblast growth factor receptor
Chr13.g15888.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr13.g16121.t1	FGF8	fibroblast growth factor
Chr13.g16203.t1	CELSR2	cadherin EGF LAG seven-pass G-type receptor 2
Chr13.g16451.t1	LDLRAP1	Low density lipoprotein receptor
Chr13.g16469.t1	FGFR2	Fibroblast growth factor receptor 2
Chr13.g16484.t1	MERTK	C-mer proto-oncogene tyrosine kinase
Chr13.g16561.t1	PTK7	protein tyrosine kinase
Chr13.g16564.t1	PTK7	protein tyrosine kinase

Chr14.g16645.t1	FGF2	fibroblast growth factor
Chr14.g16793.t1	FGF20	fibroblast growth factor
Chr14.g16843.t1	FGF13	Fibroblast growth factor
Chr14.g16965.t1	BTK	Bruton agammaglobulinemia tyrosine kinase
Chr14.g17061.t1	FGFBP2	Fibroblast growth factor binding protein 2a
Chr14.g17106.t1	-	Platelet-derived growth factor receptor-like
Chr14.g17235.t1	FGF18	fibroblast growth factor
Chr14.g17448.t1	FGFRL1	Fibroblast growth factor receptor-like
Chr14.g17522.t1	FGF16	Fibroblast growth factor 16
Chr15.g18145.t1	dll3	Delta-like protein
Chr15.g18714.t1	fgf12	fibroblast growth factor
Chr16.g18973.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr16.g18974.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr16.g19004.t1	NTRK1	Neurotrophic tyrosine kinase, receptor, type 1
Chr16.g19079.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr16.g19289.t1	LMTK3	Lemur tyrosine kinase 3
Chr16.g19294.t1	STYK1	Serine threonine tyrosine kinase 1
Chr16.g19327.t1	PTK2	protein tyrosine kinase
Chr16.g19328.t1	LDLRAD4	Low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 4
Chr16.g19330.t1	PMEPA1	Low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 4
Chr16.g19429.t1	MEGF8	Multiple epidermal growth factor-like domains protein
Chr16.g19562.t1	LTK	Tyrosine kinase
Chr16.g19838.t1	MERTK	C-mer proto-oncogene tyrosine kinase

Chr16.g20175.t1	VEGFA	Vascular endothelial growth factor
Chr17.g20300.t1	DNAAF2	Required for cytoplasmic pre-assembly of axonemal dyneins, thereby playing a central role in motility in cilia and flagella. Involved in pre-assembly of dynein arm complexes in the cytoplasm before intraflagellar transport loads them for the ciliary compartment
Chr17.g20316.t1	DLK1	Delta-like 1 homolog (Drosophila)
Chr17.g20450.t1	PTK2B	Protein tyrosine kinase 2 beta
Chr17.g20451.t1	PTK2B	Protein tyrosine kinase 2 beta
Chr17.g20550.t1	TYRO3	TYRO3 protein tyrosine kinase
Chr17.g20756.t1	TTBK1	Protein tyrosine kinase
Chr17.g20779.t1	FGFBP3	Fibroblast growth factor binding protein 3
Chr17.g20793.t1	EPS8L3	Epidermal growth factor receptor kinase substrate 8-like protein
Chr17.g20835.t1	LCK	Lymphocyte-specific protein tyrosine kinase
Chr17.g20882.t1	TEX14	Protein tyrosine kinase
Chr17.g20961.t1	LTK	Tyrosine kinase
Chr17.g20962.t1	LTK	Tyrosine kinase
Chr17.g21360.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr18.g21555.t1	CSK	C-src tyrosine kinase
Chr18.g21700.t1	NETO2	Neuropilin (NRP) and tolloid (TLL)-like
Chr18.g21733.t1	HGF	Potent mitogen for mature parenchymal hepatocyte cells, seems to be a hepatotrophic factor, and acts as a growth factor for a broad spectrum of tissues and cell types. Activating ligand for the receptor tyrosine kinase MET by binding to it and promoting its dimerization
Chr18.g21893.t1	MEGF11	Multiple epidermal growth factor-like domains protein
Chr18.g22396.t1	DNER	Delta and Notch-like epidermal growth factor-related

Chr18.g22544.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr19.g22782.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr19.g22839.t1	PMEPA1	Low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 4
Chr19.g22973.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr19.g23004.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr19.g23037.t1	LDLRAP1	Low density lipoprotein receptor
Chr19.g23173.t1	HGF	Potent mitogen for mature parenchymal hepatocyte cells, seems to be a hepatotrophic factor, and acts as a growth factor for a broad spectrum of tissues and cell types. Activating ligand for the receptor tyrosine kinase MET by binding to it and promoting its dimerization
Chr19.g23495.t1	-	Protein tyrosine kinase
Chr19.g23762.t1	PTK2	protein tyrosine kinase
Chr20.g24048.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr20.g24313.t1	BLK	B lymphoid tyrosine kinase
Chr20.g24323.t1	PTK2B	Protein tyrosine kinase 2 beta
Chr20.g24360.t1	KDR	Kinase insert domain receptor (a type III receptor tyrosine kinase)
Chr20.g24362.t1	KIT	Mast stem cell growth factor receptor
Chr20.g24363.t1	PDGFRA	Platelet-derived growth factor receptor
Chr20.g24836.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr21.g25149.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr21.g25155.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr21.g25291.t1	FGFR4	Fibroblast growth factor receptor
Chr21.g25645.t1	FIBP	Fibroblast growth factor (acidic) intracellular binding protein
Chr21.g25797.t1	FGF10	Fibroblast growth factor

Chr22.g26148.t1	CELSR2	Cadherin EGF LAG seven-pass G-type receptor 2
Chr22.g26200.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr22.g26201.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr22.g26212.t1	PTK7	protein tyrosine kinase
Chr22.g26448.t1	NRP1	Belongs to the neuropilin family
Chr22.g26616.t1	FGF22	Fibroblast growth factor 22
Chr22.g26720.t1	EPS15L1	Epidermal growth factor receptor
Chr22.g26728.t1	LPL	The primary function of this lipase is the hydrolysis of triglycerides of circulating chylomicrons and very low density lipoproteins (VLDL). Binding to heparin sulfate proteoglycans at the cell surface is vital to the function. The apolipoprotein, APOC2, acts as a coactivator of LPL activity in the presence of lipids on the luminal surface of vascular endothelium
Chr22.g26855.t1	-	receptor signaling protein tyrosine kinase inhibitor activity
Chr22.g27067.t1	MATK	Megakaryocyte-associated tyrosine kinase
Chr23.g27635.t1	STYK1	Serine threonine tyrosine kinase 1
Chr23.g27832.t1	PTK6	PTK6 protein tyrosine kinase
Chr24.g28361.t1	MAP3K14	Protein tyrosine kinase
Chr24.g28364.t1	MAP3K14	Protein tyrosine kinase
Chr24.g28512.t1	ghsr	Growth hormone secretagogue receptor
Chr24.g28606.t1	FLT1	Fms-related tyrosine kinase 1 (vascular endothelial growth factor vascular permeability factor receptor)
Chr24.g28706.t1	NETO1	Neuropilin (NRP) and tolloid (TLL)-like 1
Chr24.g28707.t1	NETO1	Neuropilin (NRP) and tolloid (TLL)-like 1
Chr24.g29032.t1	EGFR	Epidermal growth factor

Chr24.g29091.t1	NRP1	Belongs to the neuropilin family
Chr25.g29350.t1	BRSK2	Protein tyrosine kinase
Chr25.g29615.t1	CSK	C-src tyrosine kinase
Chr25.g29635.t1	CELSR1	Cadherin EGF LAG seven-pass G-type receptor
Chr25.g29676.t1	MET	Hepatocyte growth factor
Chr25.g29719.t1	FGF6	fibroblast growth factor
Chr25.g29815.t1	NTRK3	Neurotrophic tyrosine kinase, receptor, type
UN.g30418.t1	SSTR5	somatostatin receptor activity
UN.g30459.t1	FGF7	Fibroblast growth factor 7
UN.g30569.t1	AXL	AXL receptor tyrosine kinase
UN.g30570.t1	AXL	AXL receptor tyrosine kinase
UN.g30684.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
UN.g31218.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
UN.g32047.t1	JAK3	Janus kinase 3 (a protein tyrosine kinase, leukocyte)
UN.g33061.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
UN.g35094.t1	JAK3	Janus kinase 3 (a protein tyrosine kinase, leukocyte)
UN.g35508.t1	JAK2	histone tyrosine kinase activity
UN.g35674.t1	TEC	Tec protein tyrosine kinase
UN.g35728.t1	TXK	TXK tyrosine kinase
UN.g36057.t1	MEGF10	Multiple epidermal growth factor-like domains protein
UN.g36105.t1	CACNA1H	Voltage-dependent T-type calcium channel subunit
UN.g36143.t1	TEK	Tyrosine kinase
UN.g36287.t1	NRP1	Belongs to the neuropilin family
UN.g36536.t1	SSTR2	Somatostatin receptor
UN.g38306.t1	EGFR	transmembrane receptor protein tyrosine kinase activity
UN.g39700.t1	FGFR4	Fibroblast growth factor receptor
UN.g40609.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
UN.g40803.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
UN.g41096.t1	FGFR2	Fibroblast growth factor receptor 2

UN.g41330.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
UN.g43056.t1	CELSR1	Cadherin EGF LAG seven-pass G-type receptor
UN.g43259.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
UN.g44468.t1	-	Domain in meprin, A5, receptor protein tyrosine phosphatase mu (and others)
UN.g45885.t1	-	protein serine/threonine kinase activity
Chr1.g256.t1	AKT3	RAC-gamma serine threonine-protein
Chr1.g683.t1	IGF2BP2	insulin-like growth factor 2
Chr1.g821.t1	SGK494	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr1.g843.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr1.g1005.t1	MTMR7	Belongs to the protein-tyrosine phosphatase family. Non-receptor class myotubularin subfamily
Chr1.g1132.t1	PLK1	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr2.g1603.t1	PPP1CB	Serine threonine-protein phosphatase PP1-beta catalytic subunit
Chr2.g1623.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
Chr2.g1756.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr2.g1797.t1	ARTN	Transforming growth factor beta like domain
Chr2.g2176.t1	PLK3	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr2.g2270.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase NIM1-like
Chr2.g2514.t1	-	Growth hormone releasing hormone receptor a
Chr2.g2569.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase NIM1-like
Chr3.g2683.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr3.g2755.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr3.g2756.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr3.g2757.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr3.g3259.t1	PPP1CA	Serine threonine-protein phosphatase
Chr3.g3352.t1	PPP4C	Serine threonine-protein phosphatase 4 catalytic subunit
Chr3.g3476.t1	TAOK2	Serine threonine-protein kinase TAO2-like
Chr3.g3511.t1	CYB561	Cytochrome b561
Chr3.g3528.t1	IGF2BP1	Insulin-like growth factor 2 mRNA binding protein 1
Chr3.g3837.t1	MAST1	Microtubule-associated serine threonine-protein kinase

Chr3.g3896.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr3.g3934.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr4.g4534.t1	NEK11	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr4.g4728.t1	MYF5	Myogenic factor 5
Chr4.g4729.t1	MYF6	Myogenic factor 6
Chr4.g5004.t1	SBF1	Belongs to the protein-tyrosine phosphatase family. Non-receptor class myotubularin subfamily
Chr4.g5253.t1	TBK1	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr5.g5950.t1	KIAA1161	positive regulation of insulin-like growth factor receptor signaling pathway
Chr5.g6108.t1	MTMR12	Myotubularin related protein 12
Chr5.g6178.t1	LTBP3	Latent transforming growth factor beta binding protein 3
Chr5.g6332.t1	CYB5D2	Cytochrome b5 domain containing 2
Chr5.g6412.t1	CYB561A3	Cytochrome b561 family, member
Chr5.g6522.t1	MTMR2	Belongs to the protein-tyrosine phosphatase family. Non-receptor class myotubularin subfamily
Chr5.g6566.t1	MTMR8	Myotubularin related protein 8
Chr5.g6642.t1	PGAM5	PGAM family member 5, serine threonine protein phosphatase, mitochondrial
Chr5.g6699.t1	IGF2	Insulin-like growth factor
Chr5.g6893.t1	MTMR4	Belongs to the protein-tyrosine phosphatase family. Non-receptor class myotubularin subfamily
Chr5.g6910.t1	MTMR3	Belongs to the protein-tyrosine phosphatase family. Non-receptor class myotubularin subfamily
Chr6.g7338.t1	TGFBRAP1	Transforming growth factor beta receptor associated protein 1
Chr6.g7375.t1	IGFBP5	Insulin-like growth factor binding protein
Chr6.g7396.t1	MTMR14	Myotubularin related protein 14
Chr6.g7649.t1	-	Insulin / insulin-like growth factor / relaxin family.
Chr7.g8254.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr7.g8255.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr7.g8256.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr7.g8311.t1	CYB5B	Cytochrome b5 type

Chr7.g8323.t1	SBF2	Belongs to the protein-tyrosine phosphatase family. Non-receptor class myotubularin subfamily
Chr7.g8326.t1	SBF2	Belongs to the protein-tyrosine phosphatase family. Non-receptor class myotubularin subfamily
Chr7.g8533.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
Chr7.g8776.t1	BRSK2	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr7.g8799.t1	SBF2	Belongs to the protein-tyrosine phosphatase family. Non-receptor class myotubularin subfamily
Chr7.g8820.t1	UQCRFS1	Component of the ubiquinol-cytochrome c reductase complex (complex III or cytochrome b-c1 complex), which is a respiratory chain that generates an electrochemical potential coupled to ATP synthesis
Chr7.g8980.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase NIM1-like
Chr7.g9119.t1	MTMR10	Myotubularin related protein 10
Chr7.g9228.t1	MTMR1	Belongs to the protein-tyrosine phosphatase family. Non-receptor class myotubularin subfamily
Chr7.g9229.t1	MTM1	Belongs to the protein-tyrosine phosphatase family. Non-receptor class myotubularin subfamily
Chr7.g9366.t1	CYB5D1	Cytochrome b5
Chr7.g9482.t1	IGF1R	Insulin-like growth factor
Chr7.g9484.t1	IGF1R	Insulin-like growth factor
Chr7.g9656.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr7.g9751.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr8.g10029.t1	IGF1R	Insulin-like growth factor
Chr8.g10345.t1	NIM1K	NIM1 serine threonine protein kinase
Chr8.g10679.t1	TNNI3K	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr8.g10690.t1	PLK2	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr8.g10966.t1	MTMR3	Belongs to the protein-tyrosine phosphatase family. Non-receptor class myotubularin subfamily
Chr8.g10991.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
Chr9.g11106.t1	ACVR1C	Receptor protein serine threonine kinase
Chr9.g11147.t1	CYBRD1	Cytochrome b reductase 1

Chr9.g11420.t1	IGF2BP2	insulin-like growth factor 2
Chr9.g11599.t1	ACVR2A	Serine threonine-protein kinase receptor
Chr9.g11957.t1	IGFBP5	Insulin-like growth factor binding protein
Chr10.g12541.t1	DCLK1	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr10.g12543.t1	DCLK1	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr10.g12884.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr10.g13374.t1	PLK2	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr11.g14055.t1	WNK2	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr11.g14066.t1	CYB561D1	Cytochrome b-561 domain containing 1
Chr11.g14130.t1	WNK2	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr11.g14131.t1	WNK2	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr11.g14168.t1	CYBB	Cytochrome b-245, beta polypeptide (chronic granulomatous disease)
Chr12.g14363.t1	GHITM	Growth hormone inducible transmembrane protein
Chr12.g14632.t1	STK38	Serine threonine-protein kinase 38
Chr12.g15020.t1	TGFB1I1	Transforming growth factor beta 1 induced transcript 1
Chr12.g15126.t1	LTBP1	Latent transforming growth factor beta binding protein 1
Chr12.g15211.t1	BRSK1	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr12.g15257.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr13.g15678.t1	PPP2R5D	Serine threonine-protein phosphatase 2A 56 kDa regulatory subunit delta
Chr13.g15679.t1	PPP2R5D	Serine threonine-protein phosphatase 2A 56 kDa regulatory subunit delta
Chr13.g15921.t1	TLK2	Serine threonine-protein kinase tousled-like
Chr14.g16765.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr14.g16790.t1	MTMR7	Belongs to the protein-tyrosine phosphatase family. Non-receptor class myotubularin subfamily

Chr14.g17101.t1	ppp2ca	Serine threonine-protein phosphatase 2A catalytic subunit
Chr14.g17152.t1	IGFBP7	Insulin-like growth factor binding protein 7
Chr15.g18133.t1	IGF1R	Insulin-like growth factor 1
Chr15.g18179.t1	BRSK2	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr15.g18248.t1	SGK494	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr15.g18413.t1	TBRG4	Transforming growth factor beta regulator 4
Chr16.g19116.t1	NEK11	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr16.g19624.t1	sbk2	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr16.g19825.t1	ULK4	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr16.g20101.t1	CYB5R4	Cytochrome b5 reductase
Chr17.g20311.t1	ppp2r5c	Serine threonine-protein phosphatase 2A 56 kDa regulatory subunit gamma
Chr17.g20773.t1	LTBP1	Latent transforming growth factor beta binding protein 1
Chr17.g21056.t1	PAK6	Serine threonine-protein kinase PAK
Chr17.g21151.t1	NENF	Belongs to the cytochrome b5 family
Chr17.g21245.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase D3-like
Chr18.g21767.t1	UQCRFS1	Component of the ubiquinol-cytochrome c reductase complex (complex III or cytochrome b-c1 complex), which is a respiratory chain that generates an electrochemical potential coupled to ATP synthesis
Chr18.g21927.t1	IGF1R	Insulin-like growth factor
Chr18.g22082.t1	TBRG1	Transforming growth factor beta regulator
Chr18.g22116.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr18.g22437.t1	LTBP4	Latent transforming growth factor beta binding protein
Chr18.g22440.t1	LTBP4	Latent transforming growth factor beta binding protein

Chr18.g22549.t1	PPP4C	Serine threonine-protein phosphatase 4 catalytic subunit
Chr19.g23314.t1	UQCRB	Component of the ubiquinol-cytochrome c reductase complex (complex III or cytochrome b-c1 complex), which is part of the mitochondrial respiratory chain
Chr19.g23415.t1	IGF2BP3	Insulin-like growth factor 2 mRNA binding protein 3
Chr20.g23961.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr20.g24133.t1	CGRRF1	Cell growth regulator with RING finger domain
Chr20.g24160.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase NIM1-like
Chr20.g24258.t1	IGFBP1	Insulin-like growth factor binding protein 1a
Chr20.g24259.t1	IGFBP3	Insulin-like growth factor binding protein 3
Chr20.g24308.t1	MTMR9	Belongs to the protein-tyrosine phosphatase family. Non-receptor class myotubularin subfamily
Chr20.g24601.t1	ROCK2	Serine threonine-protein kinase MRCK
Chr20.g24767.t1	IGF2R	Insulin-like growth factor 2 receptor
Chr20.g24948.t1	PAK6	Serine threonine-protein kinase PAK
Chr20.g24949.t1	IGF1R	Insulin-like growth factor 1
Chr20.g24959.t1	PPP2R5D	Serine threonine-protein phosphatase 2A 56 kDa regulatory subunit gamma
Chr20.g24961.t1	PPP2R5C	Serine threonine-protein phosphatase 2A 56 kDa regulatory subunit gamma
Chr20.g24998.t1	PAK6	Serine threonine-protein kinase PAK 6
Chr20.g25000.t1	PAK7	Serine threonine-protein kinase PAK
Chr21.g25055.t1	SH3KBP1	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta1 production
Chr21.g25092.t1	ppp2ca	Serine threonine-protein phosphatase 2A catalytic subunit
Chr21.g25126.t1	STK26	Serine threonine protein kinase MST4

Chr21.g25226.t1	MTMR1	Belongs to the protein-tyrosine phosphatase family. Non-receptor class myotubularin subfamily
Chr21.g25773.t1	GHR	growth hormone
Chr21.g25775.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase NIM1-like
Chr22.g26858.t1	CYB561D2	Cytochrome b-561 domain containing 2
Chr23.g27345.t1	GHRHR	Growth hormone releasing hormone receptor
Chr23.g27384.t1	PINK1	Serine threonine-protein kinase PINK1
Chr23.g27408.t1	IGFBP6	Insulin-like growth factor binding protein
Chr24.g28340.t1	SBK1	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr24.g28550.t1	MTMR6	Belongs to the protein-tyrosine phosphatase family. Non-receptor class myotubularin subfamily
Chr24.g28753.t1	PPP2R5E	Serine threonine-protein phosphatase 2A 56 kDa regulatory subunit
Chr24.g29060.t1	AATK	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr24.g29064.t1	CYB5A	Cytochrome b5 type A (microsomal)
Chr24.g29099.t1	STK17A	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr25.g29348.t1	BRSK2	Serine threonine-protein kinase
Chr25.g29364.t1	IGF2	Insulin-like growth factor
UN.g30353.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g31643.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g31888.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g32046.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g32168.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g33006.t1	-	serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g33016.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g33069.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway

UN.g33188.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g33316.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g33317.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g33319.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g33320.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g33499.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g33515.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g33999.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g34552.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g34977.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g35724.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g35831.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g36155.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g36225.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g36372.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g36381.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g37378.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g38466.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g38802.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g39230.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g39733.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g41050.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g41391.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g41512.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g41614.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g41638.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g42194.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g42800.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g42883.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase

UN.g42916.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g44142.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g44148.t1	BRSK1	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g44602.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g44636.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g44791.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g44887.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g45329.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g45675.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g45677.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase
UN.g46227.t1	PEG10	negative regulation of transforming growth factor beta receptor signaling pathway
UN.g47451.t1	-	Serine threonine-protein kinase